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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Haipeng Zhang Wei Chen Zhigao Liu <i>SPATIOTEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES AND ITS DRIVING FACTORS IN THE YANGTZE RIVER DELTA, CHINA</i>	6
Alimammedova Khabiba Rustamovna <i>SEMIOTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CONCEPT OF BEHAVIOUR</i>	14
Amirkulova Parinamo i Behbud Jiyanov Sardor Shukhratovich Tashev Farrukh Muzaffarovich <i>NUMBER GENERATION. HUMAN RIGHTS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMY</i>	17
Asadova Manzura Axatovna <i>YERLARNING MELIORATIV HOLATINI BAHOLASH</i>	20
Azimbekova Sitora Nodirovna Turazoda Maftuna Ulugbek kizi <i>TYPE I DIABETES</i>	23
Bakhtiyorova Gulnoza <i>GENDER EQUALITY IN EMPLOYMENT IN KAZAKHSTAN.</i>	26
Gulnoza Botirovna Atabayeva <i>BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA FAKULTATIV MASHG'ULOTLARNI UYUSHTIRISH METODIKASI</i>	29
Hakimov Azizbek <i>PRACTICAL FEATURES OF FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE ECOSYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL BANKS</i>	32
Azimbekova Sitora Nodirovna Ikromov Navruzjon Gayratovich <i>MALE SEX GLANDS</i>	36
Izbosarov Boburjon Baxriddinovich Xodjaraxmanova Nazira Baxtiyar qizi <i>ECONOMIC INTEGRATION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY, ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE EUROPEAN UNION</i>	39
Mamashayev Ixtiyor Abdiqodir o'g'li <i>POLIMER CHIQINDILARI VA ULARNI QAYTA ISHLASH</i>	46
Muxiddinova Ra'no Shafoyevna <i>GAYMORIT</i>	49
Ozoda Mamatkulova Jahongirovna Azimbekova Sitora Nodirovna <i>ITENKO-CUSHING</i>	55
Rakhmanova Dildora Abdulkhamid qizi <i>INFORMATION ABOUT PASSIVE VOICE.</i>	58
Nurpo'latova Ozoda Hasan qizi <i>MADANIYAT VA SAN'AT IQTISODIYOTNI MODERNIZATSIYALASH VA DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASHJARAYONLARINING MOHIYATI</i>	63

Islomov Shohijahon <i>ABDULLA QAHHOR HIKOYALARI USLUBIYATI</i>	66
Keldiyorov Javohir <i>IKKINCHI JAHON URUSHIDAN KEYINGI DAVRDA XITOIY IQTISODIYOTI</i>	69
Saidkulov Jaxongir Turgunova Aziza Toshpulatovna <i>MAHMUDXO_JA BEHBUDIYNING MILLAT G_AMIDA O_TKAZGAN IBRATLI UMRI</i>	73
Tuxtamisheva Farangiz Salohiddin qizi Ibragimova Nafisa Turdimurot qizi Toshboeva Samida Rustamovna Omonova Munisa Shapoatovna <i>IQLIM O'ZGARISHLARI MUAMMO VA OQIBATLARI. IQLIM O'ZGARISHIGA QARSHI KURASH. IQLIM O'ZGARISHI VA INSONIYAT. IQLIM O'ZGARISHI SABABLARI.</i>	76
Азнабакиева Дилрабо Турсунбаевна Расулова Мархабо Бурхоновна Валиева Муслима Авазбек қизи Турдиева Дилфуза Тиркашбоевна <i>БОЛЕЗНИ ЛИСТЪЕВ ЧЕРЕШНИ И ВИШНИ ВЫЗЫВАЮЩИЕ МИКРОМИЦЕТАМИ</i>	81
Джураева Шахноза Улугбековна <i>КУНДАЛИК ОДАТЛАРИМИЗНИНГ ХАЁТДАГИ ЎРНИ</i>	88
Saidkulov Jaxongir Turgunova Aziza Toshpulatovna <i>MAHMUDXO_JA BEHBUDIYNING MILLAT G_AMIDA O_TKAZGAN IBRATLI UMRI</i>	91
Hasanova Kamila <i>FILM ART OR INDUSTRY</i>	94

SPATIOTEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES AND ITS DRIVING FACTORS IN THE YANGTZE RIVER DELTA, CHINA

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Abstract: *The purpose of this paper is to reveal the spatiotemporal evolution of entrepreneurial activities in the local municipalities of the Yangtze River Delta at long timescales from a geographic perspective and to reveal the underlying factors driving such evolution. The ontology of entrepreneurial activities—startups—was chosen as the object of this study, and the developmental characteristics of entrepreneurial activities in the region since 2001 were explored in two dimensions: time series changes and spatial evolution. The driving mechanism was further explored using the geographical detector. The results showed that: (1) Intensive entrepreneurial activities have been underway in the Yangtze River Delta since the beginning of the 21st century. The entrepreneurial process has undergone a stable period of slow growth (2001–2013), as well as one of rapid growth (2014–2018). The number of startups increased during this period, from 241,700 in 2001 to 1,959,600 in 2018. (2) The density of entrepreneurial activities in the Yangtze River Delta has increased since 2001. The agglomerative patterns showed developmental trends of both concentration and diffusion, forming a dotted pattern of agglomeration centered on the provincial capitals of Nanjing, Hangzhou, and Hefei and a belt of agglomeration centered on Shanghai-Suzhou-Wuxi-Changzhou. (3) High-value agglomeration of entrepreneurial activities was found to be relatively stable, and low-value agglomeration steadily weakened. Shanghai, Suzhou, and Nantong have long been part of H-H clusters, while Chizhou, Wuhu, Bozhou, Huaibei, and Huainan in Anhui have become areas of depressed entrepreneurial activities. (4) Financial strength, degree of informationization, economic foundation, innovative vitality, openness, and market demand are the main factors affecting entrepreneurial activities in the Yangtze River Delta. Entrepreneurial activities have significant spatial correlation, and areas with high entrepreneurial vitality radiate their effect to the entrepreneurial activities in the surrounding areas. The factors affecting entrepreneurial activities have multiple characteristics, and policy makers should promote entrepreneurial activities with a comprehensive vision and multi-channel efforts. The findings of this study add to the understanding of the spatial proximity characteristics of long*

time series of entrepreneurial activities at the municipal scale in developing countries and reveal the characteristics of the multi-factor combinations affecting them.

Keywords: *entrepreneurial activity; startup; spatiotemporal variation; driving factor; Yangtze River Delta.*

Introduction

With the steady promotion of the entrepreneurial model of economic growth, which is characterized by resource regeneration, productivity development, and the implementation of innovation-driven development strategies, entrepreneurial activities have emerged as a major means of improving the quality and efficiency of economic growth as part of China's development as an economic powerhouse. Entrepreneurial activities can promote changes in the market structure and adjustments to the industrial structure, increase the supply of goods, and accelerate the development of emerging industries. Moreover, they can enhance microeconomic vitality, drive employment, increase residents' incomes, and promote orderly social mobility as well as fairness and justice in socioeconomic development [1–3]. They are thus an important force for promoting national and regional competitiveness. Technological development, accelerating the pace of technological integration into the economy, and comprehensive industrialization pose daunting challenges for China in the process of economic and social transformation and development [4]. Mature large and medium-sized enterprises face high sunk costs as well as institutional costs in the process of transformation and development. Entrepreneurial activities can accelerate technological innovation and transformation, and such activities led by startups form an important part of China's current reform and development program [5]. Therefore, promoting entrepreneurial activities is important for building an innovative economy and promoting sustainable development.

Academia has been paying attention to entrepreneurial activities for a long time. In particular, since the dawn of the 21st century, innovation and entrepreneurial activities, as the driving forces of economic growth, have emerged as the core elements of productivity across the world due to the advent of the knowledge economy and information age led by the Internet and Information Technology [6–8]. Scholars have systematically explored entrepreneurial activities, including the environmental factors affecting them [9,10], the effects of entrepreneurial activities [11], the relationship between regional development models and entrepreneurial activities [12,13], entrepreneurial policies [14], the spatial distribution of entrepreneurial activities and their locational characteristics [15–19], and the interactive relationships between entrepreneurial activities and the

evolution of local industrial clusters [20]. The results have provided an important reference for follow-up studies. Different disciplines focus on entrepreneurial activities with different emphases. Geographical studies focus on the occurrence and development of social phenomena from a spatial perspective [21]. However, previous studies of entrepreneurial activities have tended to focus on specific regions as containers in which entrepreneurial activities can occur, ignoring the spatial dependence or spillover effects of entrepreneurial activities on a continuous geographical scale [19]. Discussion of the factors affecting entrepreneurial activity has more often than not focused on a specific regional factor, and analysis of the impact of regional factor combinations on entrepreneurial activity from an integrated perspective is still limited and sketchy [5]. In terms of research objects, current studies have focused mostly on a single company, a certain type of industry, or a platform for entrepreneurial activities [21], and have largely ignored their overall characteristics. In the time domain, most studies have focused on entrepreneurial activities in a single year, or within a short interval [22]. In the context of spatial and geographical scales, most studies have focused on developed countries and have overlooked developing countries [23]. Such research has usually focused on a given country, province, or city and has ignored urban agglomerations or integrated regions [24].

As China's economy has moved from the stage of rapid growth to one of high-quality development, increasing attention has been paid to entrepreneurial activities [25]. In 2015, China issued the —Guiding Opinions on the Development of Makerspace Space to Promote Mass Innovation and Entrepreneurship|| in order to promote entrepreneurial activities in a holistic manner so as to support China's economic growth. The Yangtze River Delta is one of China's most active areas of economic development, and one of its most open and innovative regions [26]. It has a strong industrial foundation, prominent advantages in terms of science and education, and a healthy entrepreneurial atmosphere. Moreover, the integrated development of the Yangtze River Delta has become part of China's national development strategy, and its entrepreneurial vitality occupies a pivotal strategic position in supporting the overall state of China's modernization on its path to transformation and development.

As a whole, the Yangtze River Delta is one of the regions in China with the highest level of economic development, but the level of economic development within it is uneven, with Shanghai being the core of regional development, while Anhui Province, most of Zhejiang Province, and the northern part of Jiangsu Province belong to the periphery of the region in terms of economic development and entrepreneurial conditions [25]. In terms of entrepreneurial dynamism, does this

—core-edge|| spatial structure still exist in the Yangtze River Delta? Can the Suzhou-Wuxi-Changzhou city belt, which is close to Shanghai, receive the high-quality entrepreneurial and innovative resources radiated from Shanghai effectively and maintain strong entrepreneurial vitality? As the most developed segment in China and the most entrepreneurially dynamic region, what are the characteristics of the factors affecting entrepreneurial activity in the Yangtze River Delta? Does the level of regional development play a dominant role in entrepreneurial dynamism? This series of problems are expected to be solved in this paper, and the authors expect that the solutions to the above problems will provide a reference for future decision-making in relation to entrepreneurial policy formulation and institutional optimization in the Yangtze River Delta, as well as provide relevant experience for the development of entrepreneurial activities in other regions of China.

Based on the above background, the purpose of this studies was to extract the data of all startups between 2001 and 2018 from the database of industrial and commercial enterprises, spatialize the startups according to their latitude and longitude, reveal the spatially divergent characteristics of entrepreneurial activities and their correlation characteristics at the municipal scale in the Yangtze River Delta, over the past 20 years with the help of exploratory spatial analysis methods from a geographic perspective, and explore the comparative characteristics of the different factor combinations affecting entrepreneurial activities in this region by way of single-factor analysis and two-factor interaction analysis using the geographical detector. The originality of the study is reflected in how it reveals the spatial proximity characteristics of entrepreneurial activities over long time scales at the city scale and the characteristics of the multi-factor combinations that affect entrepreneurial activities.

This paper is divided into six sections. The first part is an introduction; followed by a literature review; the third part introduces the case study area, research data and research methodology; the fourth part analyzes the evolutionary characteristics of entrepreneurial activities in the Yangtze River Delta in terms of their development history and spatial concentration and further explores the factors affecting them; the fifth part presents a discussion of the results; and finally, the sixth part summarizes the conclusions and suggests several policy implications.

Literature Review

The contribution of entrepreneurial activities to economic growth has been verified in various ways in the literature in different contexts, in both theoretical and positivist studies [27–30]. However, there has not been a uniform and appropriate understanding of which factors affect the development of entrepreneurial activities most significantly [31]. In the literature from different disciplinary backgrounds,

researchers have proposed different ideas about the factors affecting entrepreneurial activities.

Entrepreneurial activities cannot be carried out in isolation from the specific entrepreneurial environment, and the social environment is also considered to be an important factor, including the elements of social values, customs, ethical perceptions and local culture [32]. A study of 54 regions in Europe found that regions with more positive attitudes toward entrepreneurship had higher entrepreneurial vitality [33]. Using the research framework of institutional economics, Alvarez et al. [34] analyzed how regional environmental conditions affected entrepreneurial activities at the regional level in Spain according to the gender of the entrepreneur. By comparing two Swedish cities, Sabrina and Marina [35] explored how regional culture based on industrial heritage affected entrepreneurial activities in different regions. Daynard's study [36] of the impact of gender bias on entrepreneurial activities finds that bias against women in India inspired the growth of some female entrepreneurs. In addition, a good social governance environment, such as a solid legal framework, a clear property rights system, clear and simple entrepreneurial procedures and other institutional conditions, also had a positive impact on entrepreneurial activities [37,38].

In addition to the entrepreneurial environment, many other factors, such as innovation, age, education level, entrepreneurship, business dynamics, financing conditions, openness and public policies, have an important impact on the development of entrepreneurial activities. Of these, innovative ability includes not only the ability to put innovative ideas into practice, but also the ability to learn new things, new processes, and new methods and to promote them into application, which is an important endogenous force for promoting entrepreneurship [39]. Gandhi et al. [40] analyzed the impact of demographic factors on entrepreneurial activity using individual-level data from the 2013 ASEAN National Entrepreneurship Consortium and found that early-stage entrepreneurs were generally more capable than mature entrepreneurs and that young entrepreneurs were generally more capable of starting a business. A questionnaire survey conducted by Borges et al. [41] for the northern region of Portugal found that education was a key element in promoting entrepreneurial motivation and that the better prepared students were for entrepreneurial activities, the more likely they were to become entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial individuals have the initiative, creativity, and ability to take risks responsibly, and always interact positively with their environment in order to undertake successful entrepreneurial ventures [42]. Business vitality is an effective manifestation of market dynamics and competitiveness, which plays an important role in entrepreneurship, management,

and the growth process of companies [43]. Funding is the cornerstone of entrepreneurial activities. Studies in Asia have found that financing conditions have a significant positive role in promoting entrepreneurial activities [44]. In the face of the opening of the global market, more efficient foreign companies can break into the domestic market. In such instances, there is the risk of foreign multinational companies monopolizing the domestic market and so the entrepreneurial vitality in corresponding fields is suppressed [45]. Salman's study [46] of countries with either efficiency-driven or innovation-driven development found that public policies to support entrepreneurial activity played an important role by improving education levels, strengthening research investment, and formulating attractive tax policies.

The conclusion to be drawn, therefore, is that previous studies of entrepreneurial activities have focused mainly on economics, management, and the social sciences, while the development of entrepreneurial activities is a process characterized by spatiotemporal constructs. Although the above-mentioned fields of studies provide a relatively solid disciplinary foundation, there is still a need to strengthen research on the spatiotemporal manifestations of entrepreneurial activities and the role played by spatiotemporal elements in their dynamic evolution [30]. Thus, there needs to be more of a geographical focus on the spatiotemporal dynamic differences in entrepreneurial activities in order to highlight geography's unique contribution to research in the field of entrepreneurship.

Materials and Methods

To reveal the spatiotemporal evolution of entrepreneurial activities and its driving factors in the Yangtze River Delta, the analytical framework was built. The authors analyzed the evolutionary characteristics of entrepreneurial activities in the Yangtze River Delta in terms of their development history and spatial concentration, and further explored the factors affecting them. The detailed research diagram is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Technology roadmap for this study.

Study Area

The scope of the Yangtze River Delta region considered in this study was determined based on the –Outline of the Yangtze River Delta Regional Integration Development Plan announced by the Chinese Central Government in 2019. It contains 41 cities in Shanghai, Jiangsu Province, Zhejiang Province, and Anhui Province (Figure 2) and covers an area of 359,100 km², accounting for 3.73% of China’s total land area [47]. The Yangtze River Delta is in the plains of the middle and lower reaches of the Yangtze River. The southern part of Anhui Province and most of Zhejiang Province are hilly areas. The topographical conditions have shaped the spatial pattern of the delta, with a large population in the north and a small one in the south. It is among the strongest economic regions in China, with the highest population density and the largest number of towns. In 2019, its gross domestic product was CNY 23.73 trillion, accounting for 24% of China’s gross domestic product, and its permanent population was 219 million, accounting for 15.7% of the country’s total population [47]. The Chinese central government has identified the integrated development of the Yangtze River Delta region as part of its national development strategy, and its entrepreneurial activities and economic vitality have become distinctive indicators of China’s economic development.

Figure 2. Geographic location of the Yangtze River Delta in China.

Data Sources

Data for the startups investigated in this study were taken from the Industrial and Commercial Enterprise Registration Database, which included information such as the name, office address, registered address, industrial classification, type of company, date of registration, registered capital, and geographic coordinates of each startup established in each year in China from 2001 to 2018. Four typical years, 2001, 2008, 2015, and 2018, were selected to carry out specific comparative time–space analyses. ArcGIS software was used to calibrate and transform the geographic coordinates of each startup in the database and establish a spatial point database of startups in the delta region. The relevant socio-economic data were taken from the statistical yearbooks of the three provinces and one city in the region and the statistical yearbooks of each city. Data for the administrative boundaries of the relevant provinces and cities were taken from the Resource and Environmental Science and Data Center of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (<https://www.resdc.cn/>, accessed on 25 November 2021)

1.3. Research Methods

1.3.1. Rank-Scale Rule

The rank-scale rule is a method used in urban geography to explore the regular relationship between the scale of a city and its rank [48]. We used it to construct a rank-scale rule based on the number of startups:

$$\ln P_i = \ln P_1 - q \ln R_i$$

where P_i is the number of startups owned by cities in the research area of the order of i , R_i is the order of the i -th city, P_1 is the number of startups in the city with the most startups in the study area, and q is the slope of the regression line. The larger the value of q is, the more concentrated is the scale distribution of startups. The smaller the value of q is, the more balanced is the distribution of startups. The number of startups in small and medium-sized cities was larger.

SEMIOTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CONCEPT OF BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract: *This article discusses the semiotic significance of the concept of behaviour. The opinions of several scholars on the subject are also cited.*

Key words: *human behaviour, semiotic, semiotics, concept, semiotic significance*

Behaviour can be described by verb combinations containing a perceptual-evaluative, sign component, but the verbs in these combinations can be very different in semantics. Verbs of speech and gestures, by virtue of their semantics, easily acquire semiotic behavioural significance. However, in addition, the verbalization of the BEHAVIOUR concept also occurs through verbs that do not have such –behavioural characteristics in their systemic, dictionary semantics and are far from any semiotic actions. They also "willingly" turn into predicates of behaviour in a certain context, pointing to the "semiotization of the personality - its speech and behavioural manifestations" [1]

Semiotics is an investigation into how meaning is created and how meaning is communicated. Its origins lie in the academic study of how signs and symbols (visual and linguistic) create meaning.

The most general definition of semiotics is the science of signs (Gr. *sēméion* - sign, sign) and languages. Semiotics studies signs and sign systems as a tool for creating, transmitting and storing information, that is, as a medium that links into a single chain our consciousness, languages and the reality in which we exist. As a field of science and academic discipline, semiotics continues to be in its infancy and self-determination. This is confirmed a number of problematic issues.[2]

It is a way of seeing the world, and of understanding how the landscape and culture in which we live has a massive impact on all of us unconsciously.

Semiotics is a key tool to ensure that the person on the receiving end unambiguously understands intended meanings (of for instance a piece of communication or a new product). [3] Usually there are good reasons if someone doesn't understand the real intention of a message and semiotics can help unravel that confusion, ensuring clarity of meaning.

In the Encyclopaedic Dictionary of Culture of the 20th Century, V. Rudnev defines semiotics as one of the most specific interdisciplinary areas of our time,

without, however, clarifying the essence of this specifics. From my point of view, the peculiarity of semiotics stems from an ontologically indeterminate research subject and absolutely boundless boundaries that do not allow to accurately outline her area of interest.

Semiotics started out as an academic investigation of the meaning of words (linguistics), it moved into examining people's behaviour (anthropology and psychology), then evolved to become an enquiry into culture and society (sociology and philosophy), following that it moved onto assisting with analyses of cultural products (films, literature, art – critical theory), and finally and more recently became a methodology for researching and analysing consumer behaviour and brand communications.

The semiotic significance of behaviour is expressed in the fact that in the linguistic picture of the world there are numerous cases of transformation of various gestures, speech actions, body movements, movements of facial muscles, as well as actions that do not have pronounced sign-behavioural characteristics, into behavioural acts, as evidenced by a variety of verb in the context of some adverbs of mode of action. Such adverbs are markers of the semiotic significance of behaviour.

Behavioural symptoms are signs for interpreting and evaluating the behaviour itself as such and externalized from the inner world of the subject of his relationship to the environment, as a rule, the social world.

Compare the following statements:

After replacing the receiver she sat down on the edge of the coffee table and smiled to herself

*He smiled **effusively**, gave a mock bow, and went to stand beside one of the thrones.*

These examples of the use of the verb smile in various contexts convincingly demonstrate the fundamental difference in the interpretation of mimic action. As is known, the central feature of action predicates is the feature of controllability with the entire set of aspects of the controlled action that accompany or determine this feature: intentionality, purposefulness, awareness, etc. [4].

Although the verb smile does not belong to the central action verbs (like physical action verbs such as cut, wash, paint, etc.), to smile means to consciously move the muscles of the face in a certain way:

to raise the corners of your mouth when you are happy, pleased, or being friendly, or when you think something is funny.

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**NUMBER GENERATION. HUMAN RIGHTS DURING THE COVID-19
PANDEMY**

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Abstract: *This article describes the situation in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of a severe pandemic in the world, the measures taken by the government to ensure human rights and their consequences.*

Keywords: *COVID-19, syndrome, pandemic, government, infection, online education, human rights, WHO, Presidential Decree, business entities, economic sectors, crisis, vaccine, quarantine, hygiene, innovation, disease*

We know that the pandemic of COVID-19 coronavirus infection caused by severe acute respiratory distress syndrome was first reported in December 2019 in Wuhan, China, and on March 11, 2020, it was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization. The data that formed the basis of the research process were collected through joint research by Chinese and foreign scientists. "As of November 12, 2021, the virus has infected more than 252 million people in more than 192 countries and territories." The worst cases of the pandemic occurred in China, Europe, Iran, South Korea and the United States.

It should be noted that since then, in March 2020, Uzbekistan has a list of the first cases of coronavirus. The rapid spread of this disease, the death of many people from this infection, has led to a pandemic in our country. At the moment, the declaration of a pandemic in our country has caused concern to many of our compatriots and caused a number of inconveniences. At the same time, the process of temporarily suspending the activities of many organizations and institutions, limiting the distance and communication between them in order to prevent the spread of infection among citizens, and the movement of people in public places has undoubtedly caused some problems. That is, the transition of the younger

generation from the traditional form of education to the form of online education, the temporary inability of some individuals to work, of course, led to unnecessary contact with the external environment and a number of restrictions on meetings. It is safe to say that this problem has arisen not only in our country but all over the world.

Undoubtedly, in order to prevent coronavirus in our country, cooperation has been established with a number of countries, including the People's Republic of China, and the prevalence of coronavirus in these countries has been monitored and forecasted along with the situation in our country. As a result of cooperation with these countries, a number of the latest technologies have been brought to our country, vaccines have been developed, assistance has been provided to the affected areas, modern, effective methods of treatment have been provided and their healthy population has been rehabilitated. communication with was subject to several restrictions. Especially in this situation, all media outlets were involved to inform the population about the situation in our country.

The most gratifying thing is that a number of human rights decisions have been made by our government. For example, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 03.04.2020 PF-5978 "On additional measures to support the population, sectors of the economy and businesses during the pandemic during the pandemic" It is safe to say that the amount of income tax levied on individuals for sole proprietorships, which was suspended, and the fact that its collection has officially ceased to exist, also reflected a number of benefits. On the other hand, a number of low-income families have been provided with food assistance or a number of tax exemptions have been extended until December 31, 2020 from the Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5996 of May 18, 2020. for example, we can see that citizens are exempt from paying property and land taxes.

These benefits can also be seen in the judiciary. It was terminated in accordance with paragraphs 1 and 2 of Article 156 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and at the same time the statute of limitations was suspended. It is said that the rest of the treatment period will begin after the end of quarantine.

The decree of the state on the transfer of all organizations and institutions to the online mode did not bypass the field of education. We know that running a business online is much more complicated than running it offline. Therefore, it was a great relief to stop disconnecting citizens because they did not pay their internet and telephone bills on time. In order for the younger generation to continue their activities in the field of education, a number of distance education programs, foreign programs and programs in the field of media have been organized. The state has

allocated opportunities and funds to ensure the speed of the Internet and the quality of education.

It should be noted that we are still in quarantine, but in the current situation we have a much easier situation than before. —So far, 220,815 people have been infected with Covid 19 in our country. "Unfortunately, 1,558 of them died." At the same time, we must adhere to hygiene and stay away from all harmful environments and functions that cause disease in order to completely eradicate the disease and at the same time prevent human rights violations. At the same time, we need to be aware of the decisions and decrees adopted by our state, to study them and to inform others to prevent violations and violations of human rights in a state of pandemic. As our country is a developing country, in many areas, especially in the field of education, some quality programs are based on foreign models and are innovative, as well as further develop programs to further improve their rights. we would have re-awakened the will of the youth to be educated and to live without worries in a pandemic.

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YERLARNING MELIORATIV HOLATINI BAHOLASH

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Asadova Manzura Axatovna

Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muxandislari ilmiy tadqiqot institute huzuridagi buxoro tabiiy resurslarni boshqarish instituti o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: *Maqola qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishining resurs salohiyatini aniqlash, tuproqni baholashning moliyaviy masalalarini hal qilish va qishloq xo'jaligi erlarini hisobga olgan holda, yerlarni baholash ishlarni tasniflash.*

Kalit so'zlar: *meliorativ, baholash, tuproq boniteti*

Kirish. Tuproq-ekologik baholash va tuproqlarni yagona asosda baholashdir. Yerlarning ayrim ekinlar uchun yaroqliligi yoki tuproqning meliorativ holatini baholashda (BMTning Oziq -ovqat va qishloq xo'jaligi tashkiloti) tomonidan tavsiya etilgan reyting usuli qo'llaniladi. Yerlarning ma'lum bir foydalanish turiga yaroqliligini baholash mezonlari sifatida quyidagi parametrlar olinadi: yerlarning yaroqliligi bo'yicha cheklovlar darajasini ball (reytinglar) bo'yicha baholash – yer uchastkasidan antropogen foydalanish imkoniyatini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi yoki cheklovchi ko'rsatkichlar ro'yxatini qiyosiy tahlil qilish asosida eksperimental yoki ekspertiza asosida belgilanadi; -yerlarning ma'lum bir yerga (pichanzor, yaylov, haydaladigan yerlar va boshqalar) muvofiqligini baholash uchun eng muhim ko'rsatkichlarni tahlil qilish. Bunday ko'rsatkichlar qatoriga rel'ef, suv rejimi, eroziya, granulometrik tarkibi, tuproq sho'rlanishi va boshqalar to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar kiradi; -baholash ballari (reytinglari) shaklida taqdim etilgan ko'rsatkichlarning sifat va miqdoriy tavsiflari. Shunday qilib, masalan, reliefning xususiyati qiyalikning tikligi, uchastkaning relief shakli bilan chegaralanishi orqali ochiladi; suv rejimi namlanishning tabiati va chastotasi orqali aniqlanadi; eroziya turi va boshqalar bilan tavsiflanadi.

Tahlil va natejalar .Shunday qilib, har bir ko'rsatkich ma'lum bir ballni (reytingni) oladi, bu esa erna baholash indeksini ballar umumiy sonining o'rtacha geometrik ko'rsatkichi sifatida (LUI - Land Unit Index) keyingi hisoblash imkonini beradi.

Hozirgi vaqtda zamonaviy texnologiyalar, shu jumladan kompyuter texnologiyalari imkoniyatlaridan keng foydalangan holda ekologik muvozanatli dehqonchilik tizimini joriy etish asosida agronomik echimlarni shakllantirish jarayonining tubdan o'zgarishi dolzarb masala. Resurslarning umumiy tanqisligi sharoitida yuqori texnologiyali texnologiyalarni jalb qilgan holda ulardan oqilona

foydalanish alohida ahamiyatga ega. Qishloq xo'jaligi landshaftining barqarorligini ta'minlaydigan tabiiy va ishlab chiqarish resurslarining mavjudligini va yerlarning ko'payishini hisobga olgan holda samarali iqtisodiy foydalanishdan iborat.

Xulosa. Zamonaviy qishloq xo'jaligi fanida adaptiv landshaft dehqonchilik tizimini (ALSZ) rivojlantirish alohida o'rin tutadi - bu "ma'lum bir agroekologik guruhning erdan foydalanish tizimi, iqtisodiy va ekologik jihatdan aniqlangan mahsulot ishlab chiqarishga yo'naltirilgan, miqdori va sifatiga muvofiq. Qishloq xo'jaligi landshaftining barqarorligini va tuproq unumdorligini ko'paytirishni ta'minlaydigan ijtimoiy (bozor) ehtiyojlar, tabiiy va ishlab chiqarish resurslari. Shunday qilib, ushbu tizim quyidagilarni hisobga oladi: -qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlariga bo'lgan ijtimoiy ehtiyojlar; -yerlarning agroekologik parametrlari (tabiiy resurs xususiyatlari); -ekinlarning agroekologik talablari, ularning moslashish imkoniyatlari, atrof-muhitga ta'siri va boshqalar.

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TYPE I DIABETES

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Abstract: *The causes of type I diabetes are unknown, but rather it is caused by a combination of genetic and environmental factors. The main mechanism involves the autoimmune process of beta cells producing insulin in the pancreas. Recent studies confirm that the autoimmune destruction of islets is caused by dysbiosis of the intestinal microbiome or persistent enterovirus infections. diabetes is diagnosed by checking the level of sugar or glycated hemoglobin (hba1c) in the blood. Type 1 diabetes can be distinguished from type 2 by checking it for autoantibodies. There is no known way to prevent type 1 diabetes. insulin treatment is required for life. Insulin treatment is usually given only by injection under the skin, but there may also be side effects. Diabetic diet and exercise are an important part of management. Diabetes can cause many complications if left untreated. Relatively fast-onset complications. Long-term complications include heart disease, stroke, kidney failure, leg ulcers and eye damage. In addition, since insulin lowers blood sugar, complications can occur if you take more insulin than necessary, low blood sugar.*

Keywords: *Type 1 diabetes mellitus, pathology, insulin resistance, glycosylation.*

The contents of the article: Type 1 diabetes accounts for about 10-15% of all cases of diabetes, or about 11-22 million worldwide. In 2006, it affected 440,000 children aged 14 and was the leading cause of diabetes under the age of 15. Males are somewhat more common than females. The rates vary widely depending on the country and region. The incidence rate is highest in Scandinavia, at 30-60 new cases per 100,000 children per year, U. with oraliq.va in Southern Europe is 10-20 cases per 100,000 years, and the lowest in China, the most in Asia, and in South America 1-3 cases per 100,000 years.

In the United States, type 1 and type 2 diabetes affected about 208,000 young people under the age of 20 in 2015. Over 18,000 young people contract type 1 diabetes every year. Every year, 234,051 Americans die from diabetes (type I or type II) or diabetes-related complications as the leading cause of death 69,071. In Australia, about a million people have been diagnosed with diabetes, and that figure is 130,000 people have been infected with type 1 diabetes. Australia ranks 14th in the world with children under the age of 6. Between 2000 and 2013, 31,895 new cases

were created, from 2,323 in 2013, a rate of 10-13 cases per 100.00 people each year. Aborigines and residents of Torres Street Island suffered less. Since the 1950s, the incidence of type 1 diabetes worldwide has been gradually increasing by an average of 3-4% per year. In countries where type 1 diabetes started with a low incidence, the increase will be more pronounced. Type 1 diabetes usually begins in childhood or adolescence, suddenly. The main symptom of type 1 diabetes is very high blood sugar, which is usually manifested in children, such as polyuria (increased urination), polydipsia (increased thirst) and weight loss for several days a week. Sometimes children also have increased appetite at school, blurred vision, urinary incontinence, relapses.

Reasons: Type 1 diabetes causes the destruction of beta cells-the only cells in the body that produce insulin-and as a result, insulin deficiency develops. Without insulin, the body cannot respond effectively to an increase in blood sugar levels, and in diabetes mellitus, constant hyperglycemia occurs. In 70-90% of cases, beta cells are destroyed by someone's own immune system for completely unclear reasons. The most studied component of this autoimmune response is beta-cell target antibodies, which begin to develop months or years before the onset of symptoms. Usually, someone first develops antibodies against insulin or GAD2 protein, which are eventually followed by antibodies against ia-2, ia-2 β and/or znt8 proteins. People with these antibodies are more likely, and those who developed them in earlier life are at increased risk of developing symptomatic type 1 diabetes. The trigger for the development of these antibodies remains unclear. Several explanatory theories have been put forward, and the cause may be related to genetic susceptibility, a diabetogenic trigger, and/or an antigen effect. The remaining 10-30% of type 1 diabetics have β -cell destruction, but do not have autoimmune signs; this is called idiopathic type 1 diabetes, and the cause remains unclear.

Genealogy: It aims to understand how various environmental risks cause beta-cell autoimmunity. Many aspects of the environment and life history are associated with a type of slightly increased risk of diabetes 1, however, the relationship between each risk and diabetes often remains unclear. The risk of type 1 diabetes is slightly higher for children whose mothers are obese or over 35, or for children born by caesarean section. Similarly, a child's weight gain in the first year of life, total weight, and BMI are associated with a slightly increased risk of type 1 diabetes. Some dietary habits have also been associated with type 1 diabetes risk, i.e. consumption of cow's milk and dietary sugar. Animal studies and some large human studies have found small associations between type 1 diabetes risk and gluten or dietary fiber intake; however, other large human studies have found such an association.. Many potential environmental triggers have been investigated in

large human studies and have been characterized by an increased risk of type 1 diabetes, such as the duration of breastfeeding, the time of introduction of cow's milk into the diet, vitamin D intake, the level of active vitamin D in the blood and maternal consumption of omega-1 fatty acids.

People with type 1 diabetes should always use insulin, but treatment can lead to hypoglycemia, i.e. a low blood glucose level of 70 mg/dl (3.9 mmol/L). Hypoglycemia is very common in people with diabetes, usually as a result of a mismatch in the balance between insulin, food and physical activity. Symptoms include excessive sweating, excessive hunger, fainting, fatigue, fatigue and exhaustion.[44] mild cases are treated independently, eating or drinking something with a high sugar content. Severe conditions can lead to fainting and are treated with intravenous injections of glucose or glucagon. Continuous glucose monitors can alert patients to the presence of dangerously high or low blood sugar levels, but continuous glucose monitors still have a margin of error.

In conclusion, we say that diabetes requires systematic education from people.

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GENDER EQUALITY IN EMPLOYMENT IN KAZAKHSTAN.

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Abstract: *Women play an essential role in promoting economic and social development in a country, so it is crucial to increase job opportunities for women. However, there is still complexity and ambiguity in terms of equal work opportunities for men and women. In Central Asia, it is mostly women who suffer from unequal opportunities at work and in life due to culture, society, religion, economics and politics. Women's contributions in the economic and social sphere are devalued and underestimated. There are, however, several strategies to strengthen women in order to make their rights equal with men, especially in the labour market in Central Asian regions. This article will discuss about the gender inequality in labour markets in Kazakhstan and the change in the role of women over the last years.*

Keywords: *Human Development Index, Kazakhstan, gender gap, women, employment, gender equality.*

Introduction

Kazakhstan is the world's ninth largest country and the biggest landlocked country in the world although the population is around 19 million people. Human development Index is the level of development in three areas: health, education and a standard of living. The Human Development Index is considered to be low in Kazakhstan in the global perspective. In 2021, the country was 51st in the list with the Human Development Index of 0.825. Slightly more than a country's total population constitute women, but their contribution to the economy is lower than the contribution of their male counterparts. In terms of gender gap ranking, Kazakhstan was N60 among 149 countries in 2018, and it continued to deteriorate reaching N72 in 2020. Furthermore, the amount of benefit that women can get from the economic development of any nation depends on the position of women in the labour market. Additionally, according to the study conducted by International Monetary Fund, the more the women participate in the workforce, the higher the economic growth and the welfare of the nation. In this way, when the participation of women in the labour market in Central Asia and Europe increases, economic wellbeing goes up by about 1%.

Methods

This is both the qualitative and quantitative study that employs the literature review analysis as its main technique. The primary data has been collected from research papers, published journals and official websites for statistical data. The statistical data has been collected with regards to the share of women in the labour market and their contribution to it. In terms of qualitative study, certain terms have been defined using the definitions given by official sites and books.

Main findings

In Kazakhstan, the percentage of women participation in the economic activities in 2018 was 64.8%, which was 11.1 % lower than that of men. The unemployment rate among women also remained higher as compared to men, at 5.4 % for women in 2018 while for men 4.3%. The distribution of genders in different sectors in the economy is also very distinguished. The highest number of women are employed in education, health care and service sectors, almost 70%. In 2008, the gender pay gap in Kazakhstan was large, totalling 36%. Women's salaries constituted 65.8% of men's salaries. The gender gaps in labour remuneration differed with age groups, such as 36.7% within 35-44 years, 35% (45-54 years) and within the age groups of 65 and above and 25 and below were 25.3% and 16.9% respectively. The gender pay gaps differ as per the types of occupations as well. For instance, women's earnings in the administrative and support services are higher than men's by more than 95%. In health and social services, the wage gaps are minor, where women's income is 93.3% of that of men. In the remaining areas such as the arts and entertainment sectors, women's salaries are 50.4% of men's salaries, in the technical and scientific fields 64%.

Results

The government of Kazakhstan implements certain technical cooperation activities to increase women's participation and equal opportunities in the country. According to the laws of the country, there is no discrimination between the genders in any field, but these laws are not always practised. The absence of formal equality means that women are treated lower than men, especially in the labour market they are paid less than men for the same job they performed.

Conclusion

Although women have higher educational qualifications than men, their employment opportunities in the labour market are considerably limited. Legal barriers mean that women encounter discrimination when applying for male-dominated jobs and the gender gap remains prevalent in the country. This affects the overall participation of women and youngsters in the economy of Kazakhstan. In addition, gender equality ensures the balanced economic growth and stability in the country. Besides, equal participation of genders in the labour market does more than

this. This means that working women become independent not only financially but also within the household. They greatly contribute to the distribution of various resources at home. Therefore, it is the fundamental responsibility of the government to ensure to practice the laws to control the gender equality and regulate this practice in every field.

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BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA FAKULTATIV MASHG'ULOTLARNI UYUSHTIRISH METODIKASI

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Boshlang'ich sinflarda fakultativ mashg'ulotlarni uyushtirish metodikasi hamda dars mashg'ulotlarda turli xil qiziqarli o'yinlar olib borish haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Boshlang'ich sinflarda, fakultativ mashg'ulotlar, matematika, o'quv dasturi, o'quv jarayoni, o'yinlar, olimpiadalar.

Fakultativ mashg'ulotlar boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini tarbiyalashda, ularga kasb-hunar tanlashga oid bilim berishda yuqori natijalar beradi. Ayniqsa, iqtidorli o'quvchilarda fanga qiziqishi, dunyoqarashi, zehni namoyon bo'ladi. Bu esa boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga to'la-to'kis bilim berishda har bir o'quvchining shaxsiy xususiyatlarini o'rganishda o'quvchining qobiliyati namoyon bo'ladi. Boshlang'ich sinflarda fakultativ mashg'ulotlarni birinchi navbatda, matematika darslarida tashkil qilish katta ahamiyatga ega. Shu o'rinda o'qituvchi birinchi bosqichda o'quvchilar orasidan matematikaga qiziqishi va iqtidorini aniqlashga imkon berib, ular bilan til topa oladi. Darslikdagi o'quv materiallarni takrorlamaydigan, lekin uni mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladigan murakkab ko'rinishdagi o'quv materiallari o'rganiladi. Boshlang'ich sinflarda fakultativ mashg'ulotlar didaktik o'yinlar, olimpiadalar, kechalar, viktorinalar o'tkazishga yordam beradi. Ilmiy texnik taraqqiyot matematikaga bog'langanligi sababli asta-sekin murakkabroq masalalar yechimini o'rganishga imkoniyat beradi. Masalan, EHMda, mikrokalkulyatorida hisoblashlar o'rganiladi. Boshlang'ich sinflarda fakultativ mashg'ulotlarda o'quvchilarning matematik tafakkuri, fikrlash qobiliyati rivojlanadi. Fakultativ mashg'ulotlarni boshlang'ich sinflarda turli xil tarzda olib borish mumkin, ayniqsa, III-IV sinflarda qiziqarli, ya'ni: o'quvchilarning matematikaga bo'lgan qiziqishini hartomonlama hisobga olgan holda olib borish lozim. Fakultativ mashg'ulotlar I sinfda o'qituvchi o'quvchilarni qiziqishi va o'zlashtirishiga qarab fanlar aro aloqadorlikni hisobga olgan holda olib boradi. II-IV sinflarda 34 soat o'tiladi. II sinfda choraklar bo'yicha olib borish mumkin. Masalan, 1 chorakda matematika, 2 chorakda ona tili va hokazo. III sinfda yarim yillik bo'yicha olib boriladi. Masalan, 1 yarim yillikda matematika, 2 yarim yillikda ona tili va hokazo. IV sinf esa yoppasiga faqat matematikaga bag'ishlanadi. III-IV sinflarda ko'pincha murakkab masalalar ustida ishlash uchun fakultativ mashg'ulotlarda masalalar ustida ishlash uchun 10 soat ajratiladi. Boshlang'ich sinflarda matematika fanidan fakultativ mashg'ulotlar taxminiy rejasini keltiramiz. Boshlang'ich sinflarda fakultativ mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish mohiyati

juda katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Fakultativ mashg'ulotlarda darslik materiallarini takrorlamaydigan materiallar o'rganilib, lekin e'tibor boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining darsdan olgan bilimini mustahkamlash va chuqurlashtirishga qaratilishi lozim. Ayniqsa, sharq mutafakkirlari ijodini o'rganish, matematika darslari samaradorligini oshirishda tarixiy materiallardan foydalanish har bir mashg'ulotlarda tavsiya etiladi. Masalan,

1-mashg'ulotda Abu Rayhon Beruniy;

2-mashg'ulotda Ibn Sino, keyingisida Al-Xorazmiy, Ulug'bek

kabi mutafakkirlar merosidan boshlang'ich sinfga xos tomonlari o'rganiladi. IV sinfda fakultativ mashg'ulotlarda o'rganish mumkin bo'lgan taxminiy reja - Abu Ali ibn Sinoga bag'ishlangan mashg'ulot namunasini sizlarga havola etamiz.

1- mashg'ulot. Abu Ali ibn Sino haqida ma'lumot.

2- mashg'ulot. Abu Ali ibn Sinoning „Al-hisob“ nomli asari. Ibn Sinoning „Ash-shifo“ nomli asari bo'limlaridan biri riyoziyot, hisob (arifmetika), handasa (geometriya) va aljabr (algebra) faniga bag'ishlangan. Ibn Sino arifmetikasi arab tilida yozilgan bo'lib, to'rt bo'limdan iborat. Birinchi bo'limda turli ketma-ketlik sonlar xossalari bayon etilgan. Ikkinchi bo'limda sonlar tengligini tengsizligi bilan solishtirish amallari ko'rsatiladi. Uchinchi bo'limda arifmetikaning geometriya qonunlaridan ayrimlari bilan bog'lanish ifodalanadi. To'rtinchi bo'limda arifmetik va geometrik ko'rsatmali vositalar aniqlanadi. IV sinfda matematikadan fakultativ mashg'ulotlarda quyidagi xossalardan foydalanish mumkin. Sonlarning xossalari Ibn Sino aytishicha sonlarning tabiiy qatori shunday berilgan: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13 ... Bunday qatordagi har bir sonning boshqalariga turlicha bog'lanishlari xossalari olim tomonidan ko'rsatib beriladi.

Sonning eng ilgarigi mashhur xossasi

1. Har bir son yonidagi kichigi bilan kattasi yig'indisining yarmiga teng hamda o'zidan shunday teng uzoqlikdagi sonlar yig'indisining yarmiga teng.

Masalan, 5 ni tanlasak, yonidagi kichigi 4, kattasi 6. Ko'ramizki, $5 = (4+6):2$, bu 5 dan 3 va 7, 2 va 8 dan teng uzoqlikda, shuning uchun $5 = (3+7):2$ va $5 = (2+8):2$. Har bir son o'z-o'ziga ko'paytmasining 2 martasiga 2 qo'shilgani bilan ikki yondagi qo'shni sonning o'z-o'ziga ko'paytmasi yig'indisiga teng bo'ladi. Berilgan son 6 bo'lsa, yonidagi sonlar 5 va 7. $6 \cdot 2 + 2 = 74$, $5 \cdot 5 + 7 \cdot 7 = 74$. Demak, $6 \cdot 6 \cdot 2 + 2 = 5 \cdot 5 + 7 \cdot 7$. 3. Har qanday sonning o'z-o'ziga ko'paytmasi unga qo'shni bo'lgan sonlar ko'paytmasiga bir qo'shilganiga teng: Masalan, $5 \cdot 5 = 4 \cdot 6 + 1$ yoki $8 \cdot 8 = 7 \cdot 9 + 1$. 4. Sonlar sanog'i toq bo'lsa:

$1+2+3+4+5+6+7$ — sanog'i 7 ta. Buni $7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$ ko'rinishda yozamiz. Tushunish osonki, $7(7+1):2 = 28$. 5. Sonlar sanog'i juft bo'lsa: $1+2+3+4$, sanog'i 4 ta. $4+3+2+1$ ko'rinishda yozamiz, bundan $4 \cdot (4+1):2 = 10$. 6. Qo'shishga tegishli xossalari. 1. Sonlar ketma-ket ortib boruvchi bo'lgan qolmay, 2 tadan, 3 tadan, 4 tadan... ortib boruvchi bo'lsa. Birov aytsaki, qatordagi sonlarning birinchisi 4, ikkinchisi 7, uchinchisi 10, ya'ni keyingi har biri oldingisidan 3 tadan ortiq bo'lsa, unday qatordagi 7 ta son yig'indisi qancha desa, shunday 2 ta qator yozamiz:

$$4 + 7 + 10 + 13 + 16 + 19 + 22 = 91$$

$$22 + 19 + 16 + 13 + 10 + 7 + 4 = 91.$$

Natijadan shu narsa ma'lumki, bitta qator yig'indisi: $7 \cdot ((4 + 22) : 2) = 7 \cdot 13 = 91$. Demak, qatordagi sonlar yig'indisi birinchi son bilan oxirgi son yig'indisining yarmi bilan, qatordagi sonlar sanog'i ko'paytmasiga teng bo'ladi. Qatordagi sonlar bittadan ortib boruvchi bo'lsin: $1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5$. Qatorda 5 ta son bor. Bulaming yig'indisi: $5 \cdot (1 + 5) : 2 = 5 \cdot 3 = 15$ yoki $1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 = 15$.

2. Sonlar qatoridagi toq sonlar yig'indisi sonlar sanog'ining o'z-o'ziga ko'paytmasiga teng. Masalan, qatordagi sonlar: $1 + 3 + 5 + 7 + 9$ bo'lsin. Sanog'ida 5 ta. Yig'indisi $5 \cdot 5 = 25$ boladi. Shuningdek, $1 + 3 = 2 \cdot 2 = 4$; $1 + 3 + 5 = 3 \cdot 3 = 9$;

Xulosa qilib aytganda ushbu maqolada Boshlang'ich sinflarda fakultativ mashg'ulotlarni uyushtirish metodikasi hamda o'quvchilarini darsga qiziqitira olish usullari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Tadjiyeva .Z. Boshlang'ich sinflarda matematika o'qitish metodikasi
2. Jumayev. E .Matematika o'qitish metodikasi

PRACTICAL FEATURES OF FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE ECOSYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Annotation: *This article shows that the strategy of introduction of digital technologies in the banking practice of our country and the peculiarities of the formation of an innovative ecosystem in commercial banks, based on the experience of leading banks in the world.*

Keywords: *innovations in banking, innovative ecosystem of the bank, models, artificial intelligence.*

Introduction

It is clear that the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 17, 2021 "On measures to create conditions for the accelerated introduction of artificial intelligence technologies" PP-4996 the task of creating a local ecosystem of innovative developments in the field of stimulating artificial intelligence was identified. This task, in our opinion, indicates the need to recognize the formation of an innovative ecosystem in commercial banks as one of the current areas of development.

Today, despite the recognition of financial stability as a priority in the development strategy of banks, the automation of business processes, expanding the use of electronic platforms to offer customers banking services and products, the usage of "cloud technology" in management decision-making is a factor that strengthens, expands the customer and resource base. Based on the above and the practice of leading foreign banks, we try to study the peculiarities of the innovative ecosystem in the banking sector of our country.

The main part.

First of all, it should be noted that the formation of an innovative ecosystem requires large and long-term investments. Not all innovative projects that have been (or are being implemented) at the same time will always produce the desired effect (income). The magnitude of these and other levels of risk requires an analysis of the financial capacity of banks. According to the rating company Standard & Poor's, by the end of 2020, the volume of assets accumulated in the world's 10 largest banks will reach 35 trillion. 97 billion USD, the deposit base is 22 trillion. 644 billion USD, the amount of private capital is 2 trillion. 713.5 mln. USD. By 2020, the world's gross

domestic product at purchasing power parity will reach 132 trillion. 647 billion Was equal to USD. Thus, the assets of the top ten banks accounted for 26.5% of GDP, the volume of attracted deposits - 17.1% and the volume of capital - 2.1%. It should be noted that despite the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic, by the end of 2020, the total assets of these banks will be in France (GDP - 3,115 billion US dollars), Germany (GDP - 4,469 billion US dollars), India (GDP - 8). 907 billion US dollars). If we look at the generalized financial indicators of the banking sector of Uzbekistan, we can see that by the end of 2020, bank assets will account for 61.3% of GDP, attracted deposits - 19.8%, and bank capital - 10.1%

These data suggest that commercial banks can form their own directly affected or indirectly controlled ecosystems without compromising the organizational structure, without compromising the requirements of the law.

According to the research, the following three basic models of innovation organization are used in the practice of the world's largest banks, such as Bank of America (USA), BNP Paribas (France), Sber Group (Russia):

The first model is the formation of an internal innovation ecosystem by supporting the innovative activities of bank employees. This model, in addition to ensuring the security of information and operations, increases the level of protection of the bank from changes and risks in the external technological environment. Examples include Bank of America Mobile Banking's Erica and Zelle virtual platforms and virtual channels created at the bank.

The second model is to meet the demand for innovative developments through the establishment of subsidiaries and other types of bank-controlled companies and startups specializing in innovative activities. This model serves to expand the scope of innovative opportunities through various forms of partnerships with subsidiaries and startups, as well as higher education institutions and other startups. BNP Paribas 'Cardif Insurance subsidiary and SMART Derivatives electronic platform can be cited as a result of the application of the model.

The third model is to gain an innovative priority by gradually transforming banking activities into a technology company. The SberX division of the Sber Group and research laboratories such as Robotics, Blockchain, Artificial Intelligence work in this direction.

The analysis of the processes of organizing innovative activities in the banking sector of the country allows us to note a number of specific features:

The proliferation of financial technologies and the growing demand for them in the most important customer segments, as well as the growing focus on converting closed systems (especially IABTs) used in commercial banks to open electronic platforms to relatively reduce investment in basic infrastructure and technological

assets. Despite the high level of security risk, the introduction of software application interfaces (APIs) to open the functions of internal information systems to external users and establish communication channels with them has led to the expansion of corporate and mobile banking capabilities;

security of information and operations, creation of Data Warehouse and banking business analysis system, application of SubTech and RegTech technologies in banking regulation, introduction of IFRS 9 requirements to improve corporate governance, SAP BW and SAP BO systems in assessing potential losses on bank assets application, etc. have an impact on the organization of innovation processes in commercial banks.

Conclusions and suggestions

The conducted research allows to note the following features:

Firstly, the formation of an innovative ecosystem directly or indirectly controlled by commercial banks with large financial capabilities will turn them into drivers of innovative development not only in fintex, but also in Big data, API, biometrics, artificial intelligence and other areas.

Secondly, models of innovation activity depend on the economic policy pursued in the country, strategic goals of banking development, availability of highly qualified specialists and technological base, as well as other macro and micro level factors that influence the scale and forms of innovation ecosystem formation.

Thirdly, the entry of bigtech companies, payment systems and other high-tech companies into the traditional banking services market will make innovative activity in banks a key tool in the fight against competition and strengthening market position.

Based on these features, the following proposals and recommendations for the formation of an innovative ecosystem of banks were developed:

- In order to reduce the level of operational risks, it is necessary to integrate into the automated banking systems the software of IT companies (in particular, the scoring system) and QQAT (automated decision-making systems), which can be directly influenced only by banks;

- It is expedient to establish in each commercial bank banking divisions specializing in the creation of innovative technologies;

- To support and encourage the innovative activities of bank employees, it is necessary to include in the reward system a system of indicators related to innovative activities.

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MALE SEX GLANDS

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Annotation: *Anatomical, physiological, histological structure of the male reproductive system. Protection of the genitalia from the external environment and the factors that cause it. Problems of the male reproductive system and measures to prevent it. Related functions of the excretion system and the reproductive system. Sexual system diseases.*

Keywords: *Penis, testicle, disease, sexual weakness*

Content of the article: Male genitalia (organa genitalia masculine) are the most important and vital organs in human life. These organs are called genital organs in medicine. According to the morphological structure of the genital organs, they are divided into two groups: internal and external. The external genitalia consists of the penis, the scrotum. Internal genital organs: testis and epididymes, sexual glands. The specificity, that the common to both systems - the male excretion system, the urinary tract - and are studied together.

The development of the sexual glands of the male reproductive system begins with the penetration of the sexual systems - the sexually transmitted systems located above the primary kidney. In the early stages of development of epithelial systems, they are radially oriented, and then begin to grow. They begin to form curves, and from this time on, the curves are called curly seed ridges. At first, these are morphologically identical, and then they gradually decompose. By 4 months of pregnancy, cavity of curved channels begins to develop. In the last months of embryonic development, the male sex glands do not change much, only after the birth of the child and adulthood are complex changes in the spermatogonia and the reproductive cells begin to mature.

The testis is a member of a group of dual organs in the human body and is located in the scrotum. It has an oval shape and has internal - facies medialis, external - facies lateralis surfaces. It also has front and rear edges. The left testicle is slightly below the right. At the back of the testis, seed systems begins, and in this area, the testis consists of the epididymis, its head, the lower tail, and the body part between them. The testis is surrounded by a seventh layer of protective veil, which protects the testis from external influences.

The penis - belongs to the external group of male genitalia..

The root of the penis is the radix penis

Male penis head is glans penis

Penis body - corpus penis

Feet - crus penis

Consist of parts, in the middle of the head there is the urinary tract, the excretory part, and the seed path is also opened.

The body of the penis is composed of porous structures, which, as a consequence of their filling with blood, change the size and tension of the penis.

Many sexually infectious diseases can be transmitted through male genitalia.

We can cite many diseases of the genitals. These are:

syphilis, chlamydia, gonorrhea, trichomoniasis, mycoplasmas, ureplasmosis, genital herpes, pedicule (genital mite) and infertility.

These diseases can destroy a person's life. One of the problems that afflicts so many men today is sexual weakness. Sexual weakness can be explained by early termination (relaxation), impotence or erection disorders during sexual intercourse. The reasons for this are first explored. In these cases, different drugs are treated. Infertility is also due to the loss of fertility. There are several reasons for this;

mechanical impact, various infectious diseases, varicocele, defects of genital development.

If the causes of infertility are identified early on, the chances of it being treated are even higher. Everyone should care about their health, let's take care of health!

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ECONOMIC INTEGRATION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY, ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Annotation: *This article discusses the important role of economic integration in the development of the country, its positive impact on the economy. The role and necessity of economic integration in the development of the country is highlighted as an example of the European Union. The process of adopting the same currency among the European Union members and other key moments were highlighted in this article. In addition, the article discusses the stages of economic integration. Although, to illustrate the article, the extent to which the EU economy has changed through economic integration, the positive impact of integration on unemployment and the size of GDP, a key indicator of macroeconomics, has been confirmed by examples.*

Key words: *economic integration, EU (European Union), tariff and non-tariff barriers, single market, economic benefits, political benefits, unemployment rate, GDP*

Integration to the international economy is a course of actions among countries that typically includes the diminishment or disposal of exchange obstructions and the coordination of financial and fiscal approaches. Integration to the international economy points to diminish costs for both customers and producers and to extend exchange between the nations involved in the understanding.

Integration to the international economy is in some cases alluded to as territorial integration because it regularly happens among neighboring countries.

Regional Economic Integration can be defined as an agreement between groups of countries in a geographic region, to eliminate and finally remove tariff and non-tariff barriers to the free flow of goods, services, and factors of production between each other¹. The following are examples of Regional Economic Integration:

- **NAFTA** (North American Free Trade Agreement) An agreement among the U.S.A., Canada, and Mexico.

¹ <https://opentext.wsu.edu/cpim/chapter/2-4-regional-economic-integration/> Core Principles of International Marketing

- **EU (European Union)** A trade agreement with 15 European countries. APEC (Asian Pacific Economic Cooperation Forum) –This includes NAFTA members, Japan, and China.

We are going to focus our discussion of regional integration the international economy on the European Union. The European Community was formed in 1952. It has now become the framework for the present European Union. The European Union is a trade agreement between fifteen European countries. The Maastricht Treaty was signed in 1992. As the EU moves toward a closer economic union and a further expansion, they plan on instituting a single currency called the –Euro||. With the promise of consequently removing barriers and creating a free flow of goods between the European countries, the integration will create new opportunities and would show a substantial net gain from regional free trade agreements.

LEVELS OF ECONOMIC INTEGRATION

Following are the levels of integration from least to most integrated: Free Trade, Customs Union, Common Market, Economic Union, and Political Union. With free trade, all the barriers to the trade of goods and services among member countries are eliminated. In spite of this fact, each country can determine its own trade policies with regard to non- members. Members are free to determine the levels of protection applied to goods coming from the outside. Customs Union is one step closer to political and fiscal integration. This union also makes less trade barriers between the members of the union.

When territorial economies concur on integration, exchange boundaries drop and economic and political coordination increases. Specialists in this range characterize 7 stages of economic integration:

- a special exchanging range,
- a free exchange range,
- a traditions union,
- a common showcase,
- a financial union,
- an economic and total financial integration. ²

The final organize speaks to add up to harmonization of monetary approach and a complete monetary union.

Focal points of the Integration to the international economy the points of interest of financial integration drop into three categories: exchange benefits, employment, and political cooperation. More particularly, financial integration ordinarily leads to a lessening within the fetched of trade, improved accessibility of

² Levels of Economic Integration URL <https://transportgeography.org/contents/chapter7/globalization-international-trade/economic-integration-levels/>

merchandise and administrations and a more extensive determination of them, and picks up in effectiveness that lead to more noteworthy acquiring control.

The enormous positive impact of economic integration on the country's economy can be seen in the example of the European Union. The European Union is an organization system for the development of a joined together Europe. It was made after World War II to join together the nations of Europe financially. A populace of 370 million individuals speaks to the 15 part nations that share common arrangements that have brought an period of peace and thriving to Western Europe. These individuals pooled the coal and steel businesses to start the integration handle. In January of 1993, a single showcase where products, administrations, individuals and capital may move unreservedly was made with the foundation of the Economic Monetary Union (EMU). The EMU is based on two concepts: the coordination of financial approaches and the European System of Central Banks (ESCB) As of now, the European Union is moving towards Financial Integration with the creation of the Economic Monetary Union and the presentation of a single money, the Euro. No one can deny the economic and political achievements of the European Union through economic integration. The community, known as the European Integration Project, has moved away from a limited form of industry to an economic and monetary union. More precisely, this community agreement was radically different from the agreement of other regions. The theory of integration put forward by Bela Balassa set five shapes of economic integration. These are:

- free exchange zones, empowering unhindered trades and imports among members, but permitting them to have their possess assertions with non- participants;
- customs unions, which moreover permit free exchange inside, but force a common outside approach vis-à-vis non-participants;
- common markets, including flexibility of developments of components of generation and, depending on the nature of the more essential models, exchange in administrations;
- economics unions in which there are common rules and more broad coordination of national financial approaches; and total integration, including a single cash.

The economic core of the EU is the single market, characterised by the four freedoms of movement: of goods, services, labour and capital. Having evolved from a customs union, the single market – a wide-ranging 'project' initiated in the 1980s (European Commission 1985; Cockfield, 1994; Egan, 2001) – complemented the elimination of tariffs and quotas by curbing a plethora of non-tariff barriers. But it also transferred powers from the national to the supranational level; as Michelle

Egan puts it: 'to create a single market, the European Union has sought to limit the ability of its Member States to exercise regulatory sovereignty'.

The creation of the euro was, by any reasonable standard, a bold extension of the integration project. Plans for monetary integration in EU were under consideration from the 1960s, but only came to fruition right at the end of the 20th Century.

Share of European Union EU27 (from 2020) in the World Trade

Exports in million of ECU/ERO³

As we can see, the European Union is the second largest trade partner in the world. As a result we can see that economic integration has had a positive effect on the country's trade. Generally, the integration to the international economy typically leads to a decrease in the cost of trade, improved availability of goods and services and a wider selection of them, and gets in efficiency that leads to a greater purchasing power. Countries with the help of economic integration aims to reduce costs for both consumers and producers as well as to increase trade between the

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/> Share of EU in the world trade

countries involved in the agreement. Although, employment opportunities will be increased because trade liberalization leads to market expansion, technology sharing, and cross-border investment.

Employment rate (By age between 20 and 64)⁴

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/> Employment rate

Unemployment rate (By age between 20 and 64)⁵

These data show that the unemployment rate is not high in most EU countries. If we assume a natural unemployment rate of 5-6%, the unemployment rate in almost 16 countries of the European Union is stable. As it is known, the natural unemployment rate and GDP are closely related concepts. According to Okun's law, if the unemployment rate exceeds the natural unemployment rate by 1%, the country's GDP will decrease by 2%⁶. As much as economic integration has an impact on unemployment, it has an impact on GDP growth.

As a conclusion I would like to emphasize that, the European Union (EU) was created in 1993 and included 28 member countries in 2019. Since 2002, 19 of those nations have adopted the euro as one currency.⁷ According to the International Monetary Fund, the EU accounted for 16.04% of the world's GDP.⁸

⁵ [https://ec.europa.eu/ Unemployment rate](https://ec.europa.eu/Unemployment%20rate)

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POLIMER CHIQINDILARI VA ULARNI QAYTA ISHLASH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdá polimer chiqindilari va ularning hosil bo'lishi, polimer chiqindilarini qayta ishlab olinadigan mahsulotlarning xossalari va ahamiyati haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Polimer chiqindilari, qayta ishlash, polietilentereftalat, sintepon, termoplast, maydalash, kukun, polimer kompozitsion materiallar, polimer geomembrana, geotekstil, linoleum.

Inson ehtiyojlari tobora o'sib borayotgani ortidan bugungi kunda bir qator ekologik muammolar ham kelib chiqmoqda. Xususan, qattiq turdagi chiqindilarning ortib borayotganligi eng dolzarb muammolardan biri hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, bu turdagi chiqindilar orasida polimer chiqindilari salmoqli ulushga ega. Bu allaqachon umuminsoniy muammoga aylanib ulgurdi.

Umuman, polimer chiqindilarining hosil bo'lish manbalariga to'xtaladigan bo'lsak, ular ikki guruhga bo'linadi:

1. Sanoat chiqindilari - sanoat korxonalarida qayta ishlash jarayonida olingan va davlat standarti talablariga mos kelmaydigan buyumlar hisobiga paydo bo'ladi.

2. Foydalanish muddatini o'tab bo'lgan chiqindilar. Bu turdagi chiqindilar maishiy chiqindilar guruhiga mansub bo'lib, ular uy-ro'zg'or buyumlari, polietilen plyonkalar, tsellofan paketlar, transport vositalarining polimerdan yasalgan ehtiyot qismlari, bolalar o'yinchoqlari, qadoq uchun idishlar, ruchka, tibbiyot shpritslari va hokazolarning eskirishi hisobiga hosil bo'ladi.

Dunyo miqyosida bir yilda jami $25 \cdot 10^9$ tonna chiqindilar hosil bo'ladi. Shundan rezina shinalaridan hosil bo'ladigan chiqindilar miqdori 7 mln tonnagacha yetadi. Lekin ularning atigi 1/5 qismi qayta ishlanadi.

Chiqindilar qayta ishlashdan tashqari ular kuydirish va ko'mish orqali ham zararsizlantiriladi. Polimer chiqindilarini kuydirilganda hajmning bir necha barobar qisqarishi va katta miqdorda issiqlik energiyasi ajralishi foydali jihat bo'lsa, polimerlarni yoqish davomida atrof-muhit va inson sog'ligi uchun o'ta zaharli bo'lgan toksinlar, kanserogenlarning ajralib chiqishi bu usulning kamchiligidir.

Yuqorida keltirilgan zararsizlantirishning ko'mish usulini polimer chiqindilari uchun qo'llash mutlaqo samarasizdir. Chunki polimerlar gidrofob (namlikni o'ziga

shimmaydigan) va mikroorganizmlar ta'sirida chirimaydigan moddalardir. Eng samarali va xavfsiz usul - bu polimer chiqindilarini qayta ishlashdir. Bu yo'l orqali polimerlarning „umri“ uzaytiriladi.

Hozirda qayta ishlanayotgan polimer chiqindilarining aksariyati termoplastlardir. Ikkilamchi xomashyo sifatida qayta ishlanishi bo'yicha PET (polietilentereftalat) birinchi o'rinda turadi. Bu kabi plastik chiqindilar qayta ishlanishi orqali sintepon, qurilish

uchun mahsulotlar ishlab chiqariladi. Bunda yig'ilgan polimer chiqindilari yana qayta foydalanish uchun saralash, tozalash, presslash, maydalash, granulalash kabi bosqichlardan o'tadi. So'nggi bosqichda hosil bo'lgan kukun yoki granulasimon ikkilamchi xomashyo yangi turdagi PKM (polimer kompozitsion materiallar) olish uchun xizmat qiladi. Bu xomashyoga zarur ingredientlar (to'ldiruvchilar, yo'g'lovchilar, plastifikatorlar, stabilizatorlar, antioksidantlar, pigmentlar) qo'shib ularning fizik-mexanik xossalarni rostlashimiz mumkin. Ikkilamchi polimer chiqindilarining yana bir afzalligi shundaki, ularni deyarli barcha texnologik usullarda ularni qayta ishlash mumkin. Masalan, turli plastik idishlarning maydalangan kukunlarini rezina qirindilari bilan aralashtirib olingan PKM dan poyafzallar uchun taglik ishlab chiqarish mumkin. Bundan tashqari, polimer chiqindilari kukunlarini shisha, tosh, yog'och, marmar, granit, bo'r kabilarning kukunlari bilan aralashtirib ushbu PKM dan ekstruziyalash yo'li bilan har xil diametrdagi quvurlar, shlanglar ishlab chiqarish mumkin. Chiqindilardan olingan bunday mahsulotlar arzon va birlamchi mahsulotlarnikidan qolishmaydigan xossalarga ega bo'ladi.

1-rasm. Polimer chiqindilari va ularni qayta ishlash bosqichlari.

Hisob-kitoblarga ko'ra, 20 ming tonna polimer chiqindisi qayta ishlansa 10 mln dollarigacha foyda ko'rish mumkin ekan. Rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasidan ko'rish mumkinki, chiqindilarni qayta ishlash bilan shug'ullanish mamlakatlar iqtisodiyotining yangi bir tarmog'iga aylandi. Bu borada Yaponiya, Xitoy va Germaniya yetakchi o'rinlarni egallaydi. Masalan, Germaniyada birgina shu sohaning o'zi iqtisodiyotga 40 mlrd dollar daromad keltiradi.

Bu borada O‘zbekistonda ham tizimli ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Prezidentimizning 2019-yil 17-apreldagi qarori bilan „ 2019-2028-yillarda O‘zbekistonda qattiq maishiy chiqindilar bilan bog‘liq ishlarni amalga oshirish strategiyasi “ tasdiqlangan. Qarorga muvofiq, yaqin kelajakda chiqindilarni qayta ishlashning samarali va zamonaviy tizimini yaratish ko‘zda tutilgan.

Bu sohada hozirdan ildam qadamlar qo‘yilmoqda. Xususan, „ Sanfa Products “ kompaniyasi O‘zbekistonda birinchilardan bo‘lib plastik chiqindilarni qayta ishlab tayyor mahsulot olishga yo‘naltirilgan klaster tizimini yo‘lga qo‘ydi. Kompaniya yiliga 2000 tonna plastmassani qayta ishlab polimer geomembrana, sintepon,

geotekstil, linoleumlar

ishlab chiqarmoqda. Shu kabi korxonalaridan yana biri „ BioTexnoEko “ kompaniyasidir. Ushbu korxonada plastmassa, tsellofan paketlar va plastik idishlardan granulalar va quvurlar ishlab chiqaradi.

2-rasm. Polimer chiqindilarini qayta ishlab olingan mahsulotlar.

Qisqa qilib aytganda, chiqindilarni qayta ishlash global masalalardan biridir. Ushbu sohada yechimini kutayotgan muammolar talaygina. Ilg‘or texnologiyalar asosida qayta ishlashning yangi va zamonaviy usullarini topish nafaqat atrof-muhitga, balki iqtisodiyotga ham salmoqli foyda keltiradi.

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GAYMORIT

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5914189>

Muxiddinova Ra'no Shafoyevna

G'ijduvon tibbiyot kolleji o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: *ushbu maqolada gaymoritning kelib chiqish sabablari, alomatlari va belgilari, tasnifi va asoslari haqida yoritildi.*

Kalit soʻzlar: *Kataral gaymorit, infeksiyon, vazomotor, ekssudativ, produktiv, nekrotik, atrofik, bakteriyalar, resonator, gaymorit.*

Yuqori jag' yoxud burun yon sinuslari — havoli bo'shliqlar bo'lib, ularning vazifasi atmosfera va kalla ichi bosimini tenglashtirish, rezonator funktsiyalarni bajarish va havoni tozalash, namlash sanaladi. Burun yon bo'shliqlarining yo'llari burun bo'shlig'iga chiqadi, ichida esa suyakka birikib turgan shilliq qavat bilan qoplangan bo'ladi. O'sha shilliq qavatning yallig'lanishi gaymorit kasalligi sanaladi.

Ko'pincha gaymorit kasalligining asosiy sababi yuqori nafas yo'llari infeksiyasi yoki allergiya bo'ladi, shu sababli kuz-qish mavsumida bu kasallik rivojlanishi avj oladi.

Bundan tashqari, ba'zi bir kasalliklarni davolamaslik, zararli tashqi omillar ham gaymoritni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin, jumladan:

- ✓ Yuqori jag' tishlari kariesi;
- ✓ Immun tizimining zaiflashuvi;
- ✓ Burun yon sinuslarini o'rab turuvchi shilliq qavat jarohatlari;
- ✓ Havosi haddan tashqari quruq yoki yelvizak bo'lgan xonada uzoq vaqt bo'lish;
- ✓ Og'iz bo'shlig'i gigienasiga rioya qilmaslik;
- ✓ Shilliq qavatning zamburug'li kasalliklari;
- ✓ Bakteriyalar (stafillokokklar);
- ✓ Sil kasalligi;
- ✓ Zararli ishlab chiqarishda ishlash;
- ✓ Burun-halqum rivojlanishi anomaliyalari va uning shikastlanishlari;
- ✓ O'smalar mavjudligi;
- ✓ Burun bitishiga qarshi tomchilarni tez-tez ishlatish;
- ✓ Rinit bilan kechuvchi allergik reaksiyalar;
- ✓ Burun to'sig'ining deformatsiyasi (qiyshayishi) va natijada sinusda havo aylanishining buzilishi;
- ✓ Surunkali infeksiyalar — faringit, tonsillit va h.k.

Gaymoritning dastlabki belgilari tana haroratining ko'tarilishi, isitma, kuchsizlik, tumov va burun bitishi, yuz sohasida og'riqlar bilan namoyon bo'ladi. Og'riq peshona, tishlar va chakkaga tarqalish xususiyatiga ega. Bundan tashqari, qovoqlarning qizarishi va shishi qayd qilinishi mumkin. Bolalarda gaymorit bolganda ularning injiqlik qilishi va charchaganligi ham seziladi. Shu bilan birga, gaymorit qanday rivojlanishiga qarab, kasallik alomatlari ham farqlanishi mumkin.

O'tkir gaymorit O'RVVI belgilari fonida rivojlanadi va quyidagi alomatlar bilan ifodalanadi:

- Isitma;
- Bo'g'imlardagi og'riqlar;
- Yuqori jag' va burun sohasidagi og'riq;
- Kuchli tumov;
- Bosh og'rig'i, ko'z sohasidagi og'riqlar.
- Surunkali gaymorit esa asta-sekin rivojlanadi, uning belgilari:
- Surunkasiga kechayotgan rinit;
- Ko'z sohasidagi og'riqlar;
- Konyuktivit;
- Ko'pincha bosh og'rig'i.

Gaymorit — turi ko'p bo'lgan kasallik. Bugungi kunda shifokorlar kasallikning quyidagi turlarini ajratishadi:

Kataral gaymorit. Kasallik shilliq qavatning yallig'lanishi, burun bo'shlig'ining shishishi va qizarishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Kataral gaymorit bolalar orasida ko'proq tarqalgan. Sabablari virusli infektsiya, allergik tumov va burun shilliq qavatining jarohatlari hisoblanadi. Xarakterli alomatlari ishtaha yo'qolishi, isitma va umumiy intoksikatsiya belgilari sanaladi.

Ikki tomonlama gaymorit. Yuqori jag' sinuslarining yallig'lanishi asoratlanishida ko'proq uchraydi. Uning yorqin belgilaridan shish, burundan ko'p ajralma kelishi, burun bitishi, tana haroratining ko'tarilishi, umumiy intoksikatsiya, shuningdek ko'zlarning yoshlanishi va apatik holatlarni ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin. Kasallikning ushbu turi rivojlanishiga infektsion va yallig'lanish jarayonlari sabab bo'lishi mumkin. Ikki tomonlama gaymoritga shubha qilganda otolaringolog kompleks davolash — dori vositalari va fizioterapiya muolajalarini buyuradi.

Polipoz gaymorit. Kasallikning bu turi dorilar bilan davolanmaydi. Qoida tariqasida, polipoz gaymorit rivojlanishi allergiyalar, burun komponentlarining anatomik tuzilishi buzilishlari va yallig'lanishlari bilan bog'liq. Asosiy alomatlari og'izdan nafas olish va burundan shilliq ko'rinishida tez-tez ajralmalar kelishi hisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari, ta'm bilish qobiliyatining buzilishi va ishtahaning pasayishi kuzatiladi. Davolash jarroh tomonidan amalga oshiriladi. Agar poliqlar

o'lchami kichik bo'lsa, medikamentoz davo usullari qo'llanilishi ham mumkin, ammo bunda doimo ham natija sezilmaydi.

Allergik gaymorit. Buning sababi burun sinuslarining ta'sirlanishi hisoblanadi. Uning alomatlari ko'z yoshlanishi, shishganlik, tana harorati ko'tarilishi, bosh og'riqlari va umumiy holsizlikdir. Kasallik asosan kuz va bahor oylarida kuzatiladi. Allergik gaymoritni davolash uchun dastavval allergenni aniqlash va u bilan bemorning aloqa qilishini cheklash kerak. Davolovchi shifokor to'liq tekshiruv o'tkazish natijasida antiallergen terapiya, so'ng umumiy qo'llab-quvvatlovchi preparatlar buyuradi.

Yiringli gaymorit. Ko'pincha yuqori nafas yo'llarining davolanmagan yoki o'tkazib yuborilgan infeksiyon kasalliklari oqibati hisoblanadi. Ushbu turdagi gaymorit sababchilari patogen mikroorganizmlar va ularning hayotiy faoliyati mahsulotlari sanaladi. Agar kasallikning yiringli turiga yetarli e'tibor qaratilmasa va uni davolash ortga surilsa, u suyaklar va yaqin atrofdagi to'qima va a'zolarga tarqalishi mumkin.

Odontogen gaymorit. Qo'zg'atuvchining kasallangan yuqori jag' tishlari va og'iz bo'shlig'idan burun yon bo'shliqlariga o'tishi oqibatida rivojlanadi. Qo'zg'atuvchilari ichak tayoqchasi, stafilokokklar, streptokokklar va ularning kombinatsiyasi sanaladi. Odontogen gaymoritning perforativ va noperforativ shakllari ham farqlanadi. Birinchisi yuqori jag' tishini sug'urish natijasida og'iz bo'shlig'i va yuqori jag' sinuslari orasida fissura hosil bo'lishida kuzatiladi. Aynan shu fissura orqali patogenlar sinuslarga yetib boradi.

Bundan tashqari, gaymorit infeksiyon, vazomotor, ekssudativ, produktiv, nekrotik va atrofik bolishi mumkin.

1. Infeksiyon gaymorit virusli, bakterial yoki zamburug'li tabiatga ega bo'ladi.
2. Burun yon bo'shlig'ining vazomotor yallig'lanishi qon tomirlari faoliyatining buzilishi bilan bog'liq.
3. Ekssudativ turi sinuslarda yiring mavjudligiga ishora qiladi.
4. Produktiv gaymoritda sinusning o'zida turli xil o'smalar shakllanadi, masalan polipoz o'smalar.
5. Sinuslarda nekroz qayd qilinsa, bu holda kasallikning nekrotik turi haqida gapiriladi.
6. Sinus va burun bo'shlig'i to'qimalarining oziqlanishi buzilganda, atrofik gaymorit tashxislanadi.

Agar gaymoritni davolashda kechikishlar bo'lsa, bu kasallik [meningit](#) va ensefalit kabi jiddiy kasalliklarga olib kelishi, ko'z va quloqning yallig'lanishli kasalliklarini chaqirishi mumkin.

Kasallik rivojlanishda davom etsa, bemor buyrak, yurak, ko'z, bo'g'imlar va hatto bosh miya bilan bog'liq muoammolarga duch kelishi mumkin.

O'tkir sinusitni rentgenografiya yordamida tashxislash juda oson. Surunkali shaklini aniqlashda shifokor malakasi, kompyuter tomografiyasi yordam beradi. Aniq tashxis qo'yilsa, boshqa kasalliklarni istisno qilish mumkin.

Ayni paytda gaymoritni davolashning ko'p usullari mavjud, lekin qay darajada samaraliligi savol tug'diradi. Va yana ko'p kishini qiziqtirgan savol, gaymoritni teshmasdan (punkisyasiz) davolash mumkinmi?

Sinusit O'RVI asorati sifatida o'tkir shaklda namoyon bo'lsa, shifokor tomonidan burun tomchilari qo'llash, mukolitik preparatlar qabul qilish va sinuslarni sho'r suv bilan chayish tavsiya etilishi mumkin. Ko'pincha antibiotiklar va antigistaminlar buyuriladi. Ammo burun tomchilarini haddan ziyod qo'llash foyda o'rniga ziyon keltirishi mumkin, chunki ular burun shilliq qavatini quritib yuboradi va kasallikni yanada avj olishiga zamin yaratib beradi.

Antibiotiklar sinuslarni chayish yo'li bilan mahalliy qo'llanilishi, bundan tashqari tabletkalar yoki in'yektsiyalar shaklida belgilanishi mumkin. Qay turdagi antibiotik qo'llanilishi faqat shifokor tomonidan tanlanadi.

Bunday holda sinusga bosim ositda antiseptik eritma yuboriladi va yiringli ekssudat yuvib chiqariladi. Bu usul shifokor nazorati ostida olib boriladi. Lekin jarayon og'riqli va yoqimsiz bo'lganligi sababli, hozirgi vaqtda faqat og'ir hollarda qo'llaniladi.

Bundan tashqari, teshmasdan davolash usullari ham mavjud. Ularga misol «kukushka» usuli. Uning boshqa nomi — Proets bo'yicha sinuslarni yuvish. Ushbu usulning mohiyati suyuqlikning aylanishida. Jarayon deyarli og'riqsiz va anesteziya talab qilmaydi. «Kukushka» yengil gaymorit shakllarida qo'llaniladi. Muolaja boshida bemor chalqancha qilib yotqiziladi, burun yo'llariga esa bittadan kateter kiritiladi: birinchisi burun bo'shlig'iga maxsus eritma kiritisa, ikkinchisi uni tortib oladi. Davolash kursi taxminan 7 ta muolajadan iborat bo'ladi.

Gaymorotomiya — og'ir hollarda gaymor bo'shlig'ini sanatsiya qilish va yiringli massadan, poliplardan, zamburug' va boshqa infeksiyalardan tozalash uchun qo'llaniladi. Bu amaliyot o'ta samarali, murakkab emas va ortiqcha asoratlar qoldirmaydi.

Statistika gaymoritni xalq tabobati yordamida davolashda samaradorlik foizi yuqori ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Ko'p tomchilar, damlamalar va malhamlar retseptlari mavjud va ular gaymorit davosi hisoblanadi. Shu bilan birga, ular asosiy terapiya usuli emas va faqatgina kompleks terapiya sifatida qo'llanilishi mumkin. Bemorda allergiya chaqirishi mumkin bo'lgan mahsulotlardan foydalanish tavsiya etilmaydi.

Yodda tuting!: Agar kasallik avj olib borayotgan va alomatlari kuchayib borayotgan bo'lsa, shifokorga tashrif buyurishni kechga qoldirmang, xalq tabobati faqat o'rta va yengil hollarda samara berishi mumkin.

Propolis bilan. Idishda 2 litr suvni qaynating. Qaynagan suvga propolisni spirtli eritmasidan ikki choy qoshiq qo'shing (dorixonalarda shifokor retseptisiz beriladi). Idish ustiga egilib, boshingizni sochiq bilan idishni qo'shgan holda yoping va bug'dan nafas oling. Agar asalarichilik mahsulotlariga allergik reaksiyangiz bo'lsa, u holda bu usuldan foydalanish tavsiya etilmaydi.

Kartoshka bilan. Bu usulda yangi qaynatilgan kartoshkaning bug'lari bilan nafas olinadi. Davomiyligi 15 daqiqani tashkil etadi.

Asal asosida tomchi. Miqdori teng bo'lgan asal va aloe sharbatini aralashtiring. Biroz suv qo'shing va kuniga 2-3 marta 1-2 tomchidan burunga tomizing (ikki tomonlama). Qarshi ko'rsatmalar yuqoridagi kabi.

Chakanda (oblepixa) moyi. Bu o'simlik moyi shifobaxsh xususiyatlarga boy bo'lib, ham o'tkir, ham surunkali shakldagi gaymoritni davolashda qo'llaniladi. Burunga kuniga 3 mahal 3-4 tomchidan tomzilib, so'g boshni pastga qaratgan holda nafas olib turiladi, moy oqib ketmasligi va tomoqqa o'tib ketmasligi kerak. 2 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarga tavsiya etilmaydi.

Lavr yaproqlari yordamida kompress. Lavr yaproqlariga qaynoq suv solib, biroz kuting. Sovigach, sochiq yoki biron matoni tayyor bo'lgan damlamaga botirib namlang va yonoq sohasiga qo'ying, kompressni sovigancha ushlab turing, muolajani bir necha bor takrorlang.

Issiq qo'yish. Kasallik davolanayotgan vaqt, sinuslar ichida ekssudat (yiringli yoki yiringsiz) yo'qligiga amin bo'lsangiz, bu usulni qo'llashingiz mumkin. Yanoq sohasiga vazelin surting, keyin o'sha joyga ko'k lampa, agar bo'lmasa sochiqqa o'ralgan qizdirilgan tuz qo'ying, muolajani kuniga 2-3 marta qo'llang. Agar sinusda ekssudat bo'lsa, issiq qo'lalsh tavsiya etilmaydi, chunki ekssudat kengayishi va boshqa sohalarga o'tib ketishi mumkin.

Bu usul faqatgina tuzalish bosqichida qo'llanilishi o'rinlidir. Boshlashdan oldin shifokor tavsiyasini olish shart.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, har qanday kasallikni davolagandan ko'ra oldini olish afzalroq. Kasallikni oldini olish uchun o'z vaqitda stomatolog ko'rigidan o'tib turish, sovuq havoda ko'p yurmaslik, sovuqda bosh kiyimisiz ko'chaga chiqmaslik, shamollash va grippni o'z vaqitda davolash tavsiya etiladi. Sport bilan hech bo'lmaganda kuniga 10-20 daqiqa shug'ullanish immuntitetni mustahkamlash uchun foydalidir.

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ITENKO-CUSHING

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Abstract: *Cushing's disease is considered a rare disease characterized by hypersecretion of adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) due to pituitary adenoma, which ultimately leads to endogenous hypercorticism by stimulating the adrenal glands. Clinical signs indicating Cushing's disease, such as obesity, moon face, hirsutism and an abundance of faces, are already present in the presentation. Endogenous hypercorticism is associated with cardiovascular and metabolic manifestations, as well as with an increased risk of respiratory diseases, mental complications, osteoporosis and infections, which leads to high levels of morbidity and mortality. It is very important to diagnose Cushing's disease as early as possible and implement a treatment plan that can lead to a successful prognosis and a small number of complications.*

The purpose of this article was to review the clinical, diagnostic and therapeutic aspects of Cushing's disease using the latest available guidelines.

Keywords: *pituitary adenoma, adrenocorticotrophic hormone, corticotrophinolysis hormone, ACTH hypersecretion, Cushing's disease.*

The contents of the article: Cushing's disease is caused by endogenous hypercorticism. This is due to hypersecretion of adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) by pituitary adenoma secreting ACTH. Although it is recognized as the cause of Cushing's syndrome, it is considered a rare disease. The secretion of ACTH by pituitary adenoma causes bilateral adrenocortical hyperplasia along with non-suppressed hypersecretion of cortisol. In most cases, an anatomopathological examination reveals a basophilic or chromophobic pituitary adenoma (especially large ones). The prevalence of Cushing's disease is 40:1,000,000 people and is most common in women (the sex ratio is 9:1 in favor of women). Adenoma of ACTH secretion accounts for about 10-12%, 5,3% of all functional and non-functional pituitary adenomas. Cushing's disease is associated with cardiovascular and metabolic manifestations, as well as an increased risk of respiratory diseases, mental complications, osteoporosis and infections, which can lead to high levels of morbidity and mortality. Since they are a consequence of endogenous hypercorticism and are associated with high morbidity even after favorable

treatment, it is extremely important to diagnose Cushing's disease as early as possible and implement a treatment plan that can lead to a successful prognosis and poor results. the number of complications.

Clinical picture: In the presentation, more than 50% of patients with Cushing's disease have pituitary microadenomas with a diameter of less than 5 mm, which are difficult to see during visual examination (computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging). Of these, only 10% are large enough to massively affect brain tissue or to affect the structure of the Sellar region (inflatable or inflatable, or the contour of cella turcica).

Clinical signs and symptoms of pituitary adenoma dissociating to ACTH are caused by compression of the tumor (rarely due to the small size of the tumor) and high levels of cortisol and androgens (Cushing's disease). The latter include:

- * With total weight gain in 50% of cases or sometimes with a center-oriented distribution of fat, especially in the trunk, abdomen, supraclavicular fat layer ("buffalo buttocks"), round multi-armed face ("moon face")

- * * hypertension

- * * sensitive skin, light bruises, fragility of capillaries, purple-red stripes (hips, sides, lower abdomen, root of upper extremities, chest), pimples, redness, fungal infections of the skin, poor healing of skin wounds.

- * * swelling of the lower extremities

- * * hypotrophy and fatigue of the muscles of the proximal extremities .

- * * impaired glucose tolerance or type 2 diabetes .

- * * osteopenia or osteoporosis with pathological compression fracture of the spine, aseptic necrosis of the femoral head

- * * hyperpigmentation of the skin and mucous membranes, which is a consequence of ACTH-MS cross-reactivity, is a consequence of increased ACTH levels (in Cushing's disease and non-Cushing's syndrome) or ectopic secretion of ACTH (also Nelson's syndrome).

- * * manic-depressive psychosis, depression, emotional weakness, dementia.

- * * secondary amenorrhea, hirsutism, decreased sexual dynamics

- * * leukocytosis, lymphopenia, eosinopenia, decreased immunity and frequent infections

These clinical manifestations may vary from patient to patient. Some of them are characteristic of other diseases, such as obesity, Cushing's syndrome, pseudo-Cushing's syndrome or other ectopic ACTH secretions.

Cushing's disease is associated with increased morbidity and mortality due to the high content of systemic glucocorticoids.

Radiation: Radiation therapy after surgery is recommended for patients with tumor residue, especially if it tends to increase or in cases where abnormal hormonal hypersecretion persists.

Radiotherapy methods include fractional radiation therapy, stereotactic radiosurgery (Gammacnife), CyberKnife and proton radiation therapy.

1. Fractionated external radiation therapy: The effect of fractional radiation therapy can be seen after two years, and improvements are visible only in 50-70% of patients within 3-5 years. Hypopituitarism can be observed in 40% of patients, and a secondary brain tumor is observed in 1-2% of patients.

2. Gram - The effect of gamma radiosurgery can be observed for 6 months after irradiation. Remission is noted in 70-95% of patients with Cushing's disease. Hypopituitarism occurs in 30% of patients.

Conclusion: Cushing's disease is caused by ACTH-dissociating pituitary adenoma, which stimulates the adrenal glands and causes endogenous hypercorticism. This endogenous effect is accompanied by cardiovascular complications, metabolic, mental illnesses, diabetes mellitus and low bone density, all of which leads to an increase in morbidity and mortality.

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INFORMATION ABOUT PASSIVE VOICE.

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Direction: Methodology

Annotation: *This article provides information about the Passive Voice and examples of its use in speech.*

Key words: *passive voice, grammar, sentences, verb, noun, adjectives, subject, person, actions, patient.*

A passive voice construction is a grammatical voice construction that is found in many languages. In a clause with passive voice, the grammatical subject expresses the theme or patient of the main verb – that is, the person or thing that undergoes the action or has its state changed. This contrasts with active voice, in which the subject has the agent role. For example, in the passive sentence "The tree was pulled down", the subject (the tree) denotes the patient rather than the agent of the action. In contrast, the sentences "Someone pulled down the tree" and "The tree is down" are active sentences. Typically, in passive clauses, what is usually expressed by the object (or sometimes another argument) of the verb is now expressed by the subject, while what is usually expressed by the subject is either omitted or is indicated by some adjunct of the clause. Thus, turning an active sense of a verb into a passive sense is a valence-decreasing process ("detransitivizing process"), because it syntactically turns a transitive sense into an intransitive sense.[3] This is not always the case; for example in Japanese a passive-voice construction does not necessarily decrease valence. Many languages have both an active and a passive voice; this allows for greater flexibility in sentence construction, as either the semantic agent or patient may take the syntactic role of subject. The use of passive voice allows speakers to organize stretches of discourse by placing figures other than the agent in subject position. This may be done to foreground the patient, recipient, or other thematic role; it may also be useful when the semantic patient is the topic of on-going discussion. The passive voice may also be used to avoid specifying the agent of an action. English, like some other languages, uses a periphrastic passive. Rather than conjugating directly for voice, English uses the past participle form of the verb plus an auxiliary verb, either be or get (called linking verbs in traditional grammar), to indicate passive voice. The money was donated to the school. The vase got broken during the fight. All men are created equal. If the agent is mentioned, it usually

appears in a prepositional phrase introduced by the preposition *by*. Without agent: The paper was marked. With agent: The paper was marked by Mr. Tan. The subject of the passive voice usually corresponds to the direct object of the corresponding active-voice formulation (as in the above examples), but English also allows passive constructions in which the subject corresponds to an indirect object or preposition complement: We were given tickets. (subject *we* corresponds to the indirect object of *give*). Tim was operated on yesterday. (subject *Tim* corresponds to the complement of the preposition *on*). In sentences of the second type, a stranded preposition is left. This is called the prepositional passive or pseudo-passive (although the latter term can also be used with other meanings). The active voice is the dominant voice used in English. Many commentators, notably George Orwell in his essay "Politics and the English Language" and Strunk & White in *The Elements of Style*, have urged minimizing use of the passive voice, but this is almost always based on these commentators' misunderstanding of what the passive voice is. Contrary to common critiques, the passive voice has important uses, with virtually all writers using the passive voice (including Orwell and Strunk & White). There is general agreement that the passive voice is useful for emphasis, or when the receiver of the action is more important than the actor. Merriam-Webster's *Dictionary of English Usage* refers to three statistical studies of passive versus active sentences in various periodicals, stating: "the highest incidence of passive constructions was 13 percent. Orwell runs to a little over 20 percent in "Politics and the English Language". Clearly he found the construction useful in spite of his advice to avoid it as much as possible".

In the field of linguistics, the term passive is applied to a wide range of grammatical structures. Linguists therefore find it difficult to define the term in a way that makes sense across all human languages. The canonical passive in European languages has the following properties: The subject is not an agent. There is a change in: word order; or in nominal morphology—the form of the nouns in the sentence. There is specific verbal morphology—a particular form of the verb indicates passive voice. The problem arises with non-European languages. Many constructions in these languages share at least one property with the canonical European passive, but not all. While it seems justified to call these constructions passive when comparing them to European languages' passive constructions, as a whole the passives of the world's languages do not share a single common feature. R. M. W. Dixon has defined four criteria for determining whether a construction is a passive: It applies to underlying transitive clauses and forms a derived intransitive. The entity that is the patient or the object of the transitive verb in the underlying representation (indicated as *O* in linguistic terminology) becomes the core argument of the clause

(indicated as S, since the core argument is the subject of an intransitive). The agent in the underlying representation (indicated as A) becomes a *chômeur*, a noun in the periphery that is not a core argument. It is marked by a non-core case or becomes part of an adpositional phrase, etc. This can be omitted, but there is always the option of including it. There is some explicit marking of the construction. Dixon acknowledges that this excludes some constructions labeled as passive by some linguists.

In some languages, for example English, there is often a similarity between clauses expressing an action or event in the passive voice and clauses expressing a state. For example, the string of words "The dog is fed" can have the following two different meanings:

The dog is fed (twice a day).

The dog is fed (so we can leave now).

The additions in parentheses "force" the same string of words to clearly show only one of their two possible grammatical functions and the related meaning. In the first sentence, the combination of the auxiliary verb "is" and the past participle "fed" is a regular example of the construction of the passive voice in English. In the second sentence, "is" can however be interpreted as an ordinary copula and the past participle as an adjective. Sentences of the second type are called false passives by some linguists, who feel that such sentences are simply confused with the passive voice due to their outward similarity. Other linguists consider the second type to be a different kind of passive – a stative passive (rarely called *statal*, *static*, or *resultative passive*), in contrast to the dynamic or eventive passive illustrated by the first sentence. Some languages express or can express these different meanings using different constructions. The difference between dynamic and stative passives is more evident in languages such as German that use different words or constructions for the two.[14] In German, the auxiliary verb *sein* marks static passive (German: *Zustandspassiv*, rarely *statisches Passiv*, in referring to German also called *sein-Passiv* or *Sein-Passiv*), while *werden* marks the dynamic passive (*Vorgangspassiv* or *Handlungspassiv*, rarely *dynamisches Passiv*, in referring to German also called *werden-Passiv* or *Werden-Passiv* or simply *Passiv* or *Passivum*).[15] The English string of words "the lawn is mown" has two possible meanings corresponding to the example "the dog is fed" above. It can be used in the following two different senses:

dynamic: The lawn is mown (once a week).

stative: The lawn is mown (so they're probably not gone.)

German uses two different grammatical constructions for these sentences:

dynamic: *Der Rasen wird (einmal pro Woche) gemäht.*

stative: *Der Rasen ist gemäht (also sind sie wahrscheinlich nicht verweist).*[16]

Further examples and explanations:

dynamic: Der Rasen wird (gerade/oft) gemäht ("The lawn is being mown right now" / "The lawn is mown often", literally "The lawn gets mown right now / often", dynamic)

stative: Der Rasen ist (schon) gemäht. ("The lawn is [already] mown.")

A number of German verbs such as *bedecken* ("cover"), *erfüllen* ("fill"), and *trennen* ("separate"), when used as stative verbs, usually only form static passives.

- Schnee bedeckt die Erde ("Snow covers the ground", active)

- Die Erde ist mit Schnee bedeckt ("The ground is covered with snow", static)

- rare, poetic: Die Erde wird durch Schnee bedeckt ("The ground is being covered with snow", dynamic)

- but not: *Die Straße wird mit Trümmern bedeckt. (The English equivalent would be equally incorrect: *"The street is being covered with rubble.")

- correct: Die Straße ist mit Trümmern bedeckt. ("The street is covered with rubble.") [17][18]

In English, the passive voice expressed with the auxiliary verb "get" rather than "be" ("get-passive") expresses a dynamic rather than a static meaning. But when the auxiliary verb "be" is used, the main verb can have either a dynamic or static meaning as shown below (including copies of some examples from above):

The dog gets fed twice a day. (dynamic)

The dog is fed (twice a day). (dynamic)

The dog is fed (so we can leave now). (stative)

The couple got married last spring. (dynamic)

The marriage was celebrated last spring. (dynamic)

It is agreed that laws were invented for the safety of citizens. (stative)

Verbs that typically express static meaning can show dynamic meaning when used in the passive formed with *get*, for example *be known* (static) vs. *get known* (dynamic):

Zoltan is known for hosting big parties. (static).

Get your foot in the door, get known. (dynamic)

In short, there is information about the use of Passive Voice and its use in speech.

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that the passive is useful when the receiver of the action is more important than the doer[...] The passive is also useful when the doer is unknown, unimportant, or perhaps too obvious to be worth mentioning.

MADANIYAT VA SAN'AT IQTISODIYOTNI MODERNIZATSIYALASH VA DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASHJARAYONLARINING MOHIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Mmaqolada madaniyat va san'at mamlakat iqtisodiyotini modernizatsiyalash va diversifikatsiyalash jarayonlarining mazmun-mohiyati hamda iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash jarayoni ishlab chiqarishga ta'siri yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlari: modernizatsiyalash, diversifikatsiyalash, urbanizatsiya, iqtisod, industriyalashtirish, ishlab chiqarish.

Mamlakatimizda amalga oshirilayotgan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy o'zgarishlarning tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, qo'lga kiritilayotgan yutuq va muvaffaqiyatlar asosida iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash jarayonining o'rni ahamiyatli hisoblanadi. Shunga ko'ra, hozirda modernizatsiya jarayonining nazariy va metodologik asoslarini tadqiq etish dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Modernizatsiya – an'anaviy jamiyatning ilg'or, industrial jihatdan taraqqiy etgan jamiyatga aylanishini ta'minlovchi ijtimoiy- tarixiy jarayondir. Zamonaviy modernizatsiya jarayoni jahondagi texnologik va ijtimoiy o'zgarishlarning impulsi bo'lib xizmat qiluvchi asosiy, –o'zagi iqtisodiyotlarga nisbatan teng huquqli mavqega erishishni anglatadi. Umuman olganda, modernizatsiya an'anaviy jamiyatdan industriallashtirish, yirik mashinalashtirish ishlab chiqarishga hamda ijtimoiy jarayonlarni qonunlarga tayangan holda oqilona boshqarishga asoslangan jamiyatga o'tish jarayonlarini namoyon etadi. Nazariyada modernizatsiya deganda –an'anaviy tarzda yopiq jamiyatga qarama-qarshi o'laroq –zamonaviy ochiq tarzda jamiyatni shakllantirishga olib keluvchi industriyalashtirish, urbanizatsiya, umumiy ta'lim, vakolatli siyosiy hokimiyat tizimlarining qaror topishi, hududiy va ijtimoiy safarbarlikning kuchayishi kabi jarayonlarning majmui tushuniladi. Modernizatsiya jarayoni doirasida odatda quyidagi o'zgarishlar ro'y beradi:

- 1) ijtimoiy munosabatlar butun tizimining takomillashuvi va turmush tarzining o'zgarishi – ixtiloflarni tartibga soluvchi hamda ijtimoiy muammolarni hal etuvchi yangi tartib va mexanizmlarning paydo bo'lishi;
- 2) alohida individlarning ongliligi va mustaqilligining oshishi;
- 3) iqtisodiyot sohasida – tovar-pul munosabatlarining eng yuqori darajada yoyilishi, yangi ilg'or texnologiyalarning paydo bo'lishi, boshqaruvchilar va

yollanma xodimlarning kasbiy ixtisoslashuvining yuqori darajasiga yetishi.

Umuman olganda, modernizatsiya juda keng tushuncha bo'lib, bugungi kunda uni jamiyat hayotining turli jabhalarini tubdan o'zgartirish, yangilash, bu borada taraqqiyotni jahondagi mavjud ilg'or andozalar tomon yo'naltirish va takomillashtirish jarayonlarining majmui sifatida ifodalash mumkin.

Yuqoridagilardan ko'rinadiki, modernizatsiyalash jarayonlari mamlakatimiz hayotining deyarli barcha jabhalarini qamrab oladi. Ayniqsa, mazkur yo'nalishlar orasida iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash muhim o'rin tutadi. Zero, milliy iqtisodiyotning barqaror va samarali amal qilishini ta'minlash, uni jahonning rivojlangan mamlakatlari taraqqiyoti darajasiga olib chiqish, turli siyosiy va iqtisodiy o'zgarishlar, jahon bozori konyunkturasidagi tebranishlar, inqiroz holatlariga nisbatan –chidamliligi, mustaqil rivojlana olish imkoniyati va salohiyatlari aynan iqtisodiyotdagi tub islohotlar va ularning natijalariga bog'liqdir. Shu bilan birga iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash ijtimoiy hayotning boshqa sohalaridagi o'zgarishlarga chambarchas bog'liq. Ya'ni, barcha soha va jabhalar o'rtasida jadal isloh etish va modernizatsiyalash jarayonlarining amalga oshirilishida izchillik va mantiqiy muvozanatni ta'minlashga harakat qilish lozim. Shu o'rinda modernizatsiyalash jarayonining jamiyat har bir a'zosining ongliligi va mustaqilligini oshirishdagi o'rniga alohida e'tibor qaratish lozim, deb hisoblaymiz.

Chunki, iqtisodiyot hamda mamlakat hayotining boshqa sohalarini modernizatsiyalash eng avvalo ushbu jarayonlarda ishtirok etuvchi, ularni amalga oshiruvchi va doimiy ravishda takomillashtirib boruvchi jamiyat a'zolari dunyoqarashi, tafakkurining o'zgarishi, ularning demokratik va tub islohot jarayonlaridagi faolligi oshishiga bevosita bog'liqdir.

Diversifikatsiya – ishlab chiqarishning samaradorligini oshirish, mahsulot va xizmatlarni sotish bozorlarini kengaytirish maqsadida tarmoq va korxonalar faoliyat sohalarini kengaytirish, mahsulot va xizmatlar assortimentlarini ko'paytirish hisoblanadi. Diversifikatsiya jarayoni iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarida olib borilayotgan modernizatsiya va tarkibiy o'zgarishlar bilan bevosita uyg'unlashgan.

Iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish va liberallashtirishning asosida albatta tarkibiy o'zgartirishlarni chuqurlashtirish, milliy iqtisodiyotning yetakchi tarmoqlarini modernizatsiya va diversifikatsiya qilish hisobiga uning raqobatbardoshligini oshirish masalasi turadi.

Iqtisodiyot tarkibida sanoatning rivojlanishi dinamikasidagi muhim o'zgarish sifatida korxonalar va ishlab chiqarishni modernizatsiyalash, texnik va texnologik yangilanish asosida sanoatda chuqur tarkibiy o'zgarishlar va diversifikatsiyaning amalga oshirilgani hisoblanadi.

Sanoat siyosatidagi asosiy ustuvorlik institutsional islohotlarning sifatini oshirish va tadbirkorlik faoliyatiga keng yo'l ochib berish, sanoat ishlab chiqarishni modernizatsiyalash va diversifikatsiyalash, iqtisodiyotning real sektori korxonalarini qo'llab-quvvatlash, o'rta va uzoq muddatda sanoatni rivojlantirish bo'yicha dasturiy chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirishga qaratildi.

Davlatimiz rahbari tomonidan Harakatlar strategiyasida yuqori texnologiyali qayta ishlash tarmoqlarini, eng avvalo, mahalliy xom ashyo resurslarini chuqur qayta ishlash asosida yuqori qo'shimcha qiymatli tayyor mahsulot ishlab chiqarishni jadal rivojlantirishga qaratilgan sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga o'tkazish orqali sanoatni yanada modernizatsiya va diversifikatsiya qilish zarurati alohida ta'kidlandi.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, umuman olganda, ishlab chiqarishni modernizatsiya va diversifikatsiya qilish ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarining kamayishiga, masulot tannarxining kamayishida hal qiluvchi rolni egallaydi.

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ABDULLA QAHHOR HIKOYALARI USLUBIYATI.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalarida qo'llanilgan so'zlar, birikmalar va iboralarni tahlilga tortiladi. Yozuvchining so'z tanlash mahorati haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Abdulla Qahhor ijodi, hikoya, badiiy so'z, badiiy tahlil, obrazli.

KIRISH

Har bir ijod sohibi bevosita so'zga murojaat qiladi. Adabiyotning quroli bo'lmish so'z yordamida o'zining xayoliy olamini oq qog'ozga tushiradi va shu tarzda yangi bir asar dunyo yuzini ko'radi. Adibning o'z asarlarida qo'llagan so'z va iboralari qaysidir ma'noda uning ma'naviy olamini ochib berishga xizmat qiladi. Bu haqida Abdulla Qodiriy: –Yozuvchini, garchi shaxsan tanilmasa ham, asarlarini o'qib, qanday tabiatli shaxs ekanini g'oyibona bilish, tasavvur qilish mumkin. Chunki u asarlarida, asosan o'z tabiatini, ruhini tasvirlaydi || [1]. Shunday yozuvchilarimizdan biri bu – Abdulla Qahhordir.

ASOSIY QISM

Abdulla Qahhorning asarlarida tasvirlangan so'zlar miqdorini ko'rib hayratda qolmaslikning iloji yo'q. Abdulla Qahhor asarlarida ishlatilgan so'zlar ko'lami kamlihi va ma'noning kengligi o'zaro uyg'unlashib go'zal badiiyat yaratgan. Yozuvchi so'zga shunchalik xasiski, agar bu mitti durdonalarning har birini qayta hikoya qilgudek bo'lsa, hikoyaning o'zidan ko'ra ancha ko'p joyni egallagan bo'lar edi, yozuvchi tilining hayratomuz ramziyligini, o'z qahramonlari qalbiga teran kirib borishini, ularning qayg'u va alamlariga chuqur insoniy munosabatda bo'lishini aytmasizmi?! Misol uchun –O'g'ri || hikoyasini olaylik. Qobil boboning ho'kizini o'g'ri urib ketgan ... Chol ellikboshiga arz qilib boradi. Albatta, ellikboshinikiga quruq qo'l bilan borib bo'lmaydi. Sovg'ani olib ellikboshi bu haqda mingboshiga xabar berajagini aytadi, o'z-o'zidan ma'lumki, bu ish ham sovg'asiz bitishi qiyin. Har qalay, sovg'a o'z kuchini ko'rsatmay qolmaydi: mingboshi qoziga xabar qilishga va'da beradi. Shunda busiz ham ro'shnolik nimaligini bilmagan cholning –qora kun || ga atab olib qo'ygan so'nggi bisotlarini oxirigacha qoqib –suqib olib borishdan o'zga chorasi qolmaydi... To'rachilikka asoslangan mazkur jamiyatning eng yuqori, mo'tabar dargohiga yetganda Qobil bobo o'sha davr uchun mutlaqo xos bo'lgan birgina javobni eshitadi: – Ho'kizing yo'qolmasdan ilgari bormidi o'zi? || Juda katta

fosh etuvchi kuchga ega bo'lgan, hayotning og'ir yuki ostida ezilib, adoyi tamom bo'lgan bir kichik odamga nisbatan mehr va xayrixohlik hissi bilan sug'orilgan bu hikoya bor- yo'g'i uch betdan iborat , xolos ! [2] Lekin shu ixchamlik bag'rida olam-olam ma'no mujassam . Abdulla Qahhorning –Nurli cho'qqilar|| hikoyasida ham yozuvchining ijodiy mahorati yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. Bu hikoyada to'qqizinchi sinfning a'lochi qizlaridan, ota-onasiga rahmatlar eshittirgan qiz (Zuhra) birdan yo'qolib qoladi. Yozuvchi farzandi yo'qolgan ota-ona holatini shunday tasvirlaydi: –Chol-kampir boshqa xunuk xayollarga bormaslik uchun bir-birini ovutdi: Zuhra qoqvosh, ta'bi nozik, dimog'dor qiz bo'lib, maktabdoshlariga qo'shilmas edi, shahardan lola terгани chiqqan qizlardan birontasi ta'biga yoqib, o'sha bilan ketgan bo'lsa ajab emas . (–Biron yigit bilan qochib ketmadimikan|| , deganda til bormas edi.) Ko'ngliga yo'l berish mumkin bo'lgan va birdan bir xayriyatli gumon shu bo'lib qoldi|| . Yuqorida ko'rsatilgan satrdagi har bir so'z ortida ma'no yashirin. Bu ma'nolardan asosiysi: o'zbek qizlarining iffati va hayosi hamda ota-onaning elu yurt oldidagi nomusidir. Chunki har birimizga ma'lumki, o'zbek xonadonida qiz farzandning birdan yo'q bo'lib qolishi oddiy hodisa emas. Shu narsani teran anglagan yozuvchi bu hodisani –xayriyatli gumon|| tarzida qisqalik ortiga mohirona yashirgan. Abdulla Qahhor asarlariga qisqalik bilan birgalikda soddalik va jo'nlikni ham uyg'unlashtira olgan yozuvchidir. Buni uning –Mahalla|| nomli hikoyasi misolida ham ko'rishimiz mumkin. Hikoya Hikmat buvaning ayoli, Rohat buvining vafoti bilan boshlanadi. Yozuvchi bu jarayonni shunday tasvirlaydi: –Kampir shu yotganicha ertasiga ham turgisi kelmadi, indiniga turolmadi, uchinchi kuni yuragi birpas qattiq urib turdi-yu, birdan bo'shshib, o'ldi–qoldi ...|| Abdulla Qahhor qahramon o'limigacha bo'lgan uch kunni shu darajada soddalik va qisqalik bilan tasvirlaganki, bir qarashda kitobxoniga ta'sirsizdek tuyuladi. Lekin jummalarni takror o'qigan va mag'zini chaqqan kitobxon qisqalik va chuqur mazmun uyg'unlashuviga guvoh bo'ladi. Hikoya davomida ayolidan ayrilgan Hikmat buvaning holatini tasvirlashda quyidagi jumla qo'llanadi: –... har bir tovush o'lim bo'lib uning miya qopqog'ini chertar edi|| . Qarigan chog'ida suyangan insonidan ayrilgan qahramon kechinmalarini tasvirlashda qisqalik va chuqur mazmun uyg'unlashuvidan iborat shu kabi birliklardan foydalanish, uni o'qiguvchi inson onggi va qalbiga ta'sirchan qilib yetkazish Abdulla Qahhorning mahoratidan darakdir . Abdulla Qahhor uchun uning –Qisqalik – iste'dodning singlisi|| degan iborasi juda aziz edi. Suhbatlaridan birida u –Bemor|| hikoyasining birinchi jumlasini qanday yozilganini , o'ttizga yaqin varag'ini qora qilib (Abdulla Qahhor yozilgan so'zining ustidan chiziq tortmas edi , jumla buzilsa so'z yoki harf xato bo'lsa , yangi varaqqa yozib chiqar edi), nihoyat eng qisqa, eng aniq ifoda topganini aytib bergan edi: –Sotvoldining xotini og'rib qoldi|| .|| Bu jumlaning fazilati , -degan edi , - fikr to'rtta so'zda bayon. qilingan || [3].

XULOSA

—Bemor|| hikoyasida nafaqat soʻzlar va gaplar, balki, hikoya sarlavhasida ham chuqur maʼno mavjud. Garchi hikoya nomi beshta harf va beshta tovushdan iborat boʻlsa-da, u kitobxonni uzoq mushohada qilishga chorlaydi. Ushbu hikoyani oʻqigan inson anglaydiki, yozuvchi hikoyadan koʻra hikoya nomiga koʻproq ter toʻkkan. Chunki, Abdulla Qahhor qisqalik yordamida insonni fikrlashga chorlaydigan asarlar yaratishning xaqiqiy ustasi, shu tufayli u uchun asardagi mayda detallardan tortib sarlavhagacha muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Abdulla Qahhor asarlari, xususan, mashhur hikoyalarining sehri ularda hayot haqiqatining hamda baʼzi holatlarda hayot haqiqatidan ham koʻra badiiy haqiqatning kuchliroq, chuqurroq teranroq ekanligidir [4].

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*Xitoy Xalq Respublikasi. Shanxi provinsiyasi
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Annotatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada Ikkinchi jahon urushidan keyingi davrda Xitoy iqtisodiyoti, Ikkinchi jahon urushining Xitoy uchun oqibatlari, Xitoy iqtisodiy islohot davomida bozorxo_jaligini yo_lga qo_ygan davlatlarning tajribalari va urushdan keyin Xitoy Sovet davlati bilan yaqin munosabatlari haqida to'liq bayon etilgan.*

Kalit So'zlar: *iqtisodiy taraqqiyot, bozor munosabatlari, iqtisodiy islohotning yangi bosqichi, xo_jalik tizimi.*

KIRISH:

Xitoyning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga ta'sir qilayotgan eng muhim muammolardan biri mamlakatning to_g'ri iqtisodiy siyosati va bu iqtisodiy islohot davomida tashkil etilgan iqtisodiy qonunlardir. Xitoy iqtisodiy islohot mobaynida bozorxo_jaligini tashkil etilgan davlatlarning malakalarini ijodiy o'rganib, o_tgan yillar mobaynida iqtisodiy munosabatlarni tartibga soladigan ko'pgina qonun, nizom, qoida va qarorlarni qabul qildi va ularni yangidan tashkil etgan iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy munosabatlar xarakteriga moslashtirib, vaqti-vaqti bilan tuzatib bordi. Ushbu qonunlar islohot natijalarini himoya qilish va mustahkamlashni, bozor munosabatlariga oson o_tish va uning doimiy takomillashishni kafolatlagan.

ASOSIY QISM:

Ikkinchi jahon urushi arafasida Xitoyda amalda 3 ta hokimiyat bor edi. Bular 1) Xitoydagi Yaponiya ma'muriyati; 2) mamlakat shimoli va shimoli-sharqida qaror topgan Xitoy Kommunistik partiyasi boshchiligidagi hokimiyat; 3) mamlakat janubi-g_arbidagi Chan Kayshi hukumatidir. Yaponiya tor-mor qilingach, uning Xitoydagi ma'muriyati ham vayron bo'ldi. 1946-yilning yoz oyida Gomindan armiyasi Xitoy armiyasi egallab turgan hududga hujum qildi. Shu tariqa fuqarolar urushi boshlandi. Mazkur urush 1949-yilning kuzigacha davom etdi. Nihoyat, urushda Gomindan armiyasi mag'lub bo'ldi. Uning qolgan qismi Chan Kayshi boshchiligida Tayvan orolida joylashib oldi. Xitoy hokimiyatni to_liq egallangach, 1949-yilning 1- oktabrida Xitoy Xalq Respublikasi tashkil qilindi.

Xitoy Xalq Respublikasi davlatda sotsializm qurilishini e'lon qildi. 1950-yil 30-iyundagi qonun doirasidagi islohot natijasida katta yer egaligi tugatildi.

Dehqonlarga 47 mln ga yer bo'lib berildi. 1950-yilda Tibet bosib olindi. Dalaylama Hindistonga qochdi. 1956- yilgacha qishloq xo'jaligi shirkatlari tuzildi. Bir vaqtning o'zida mamlakatda industrilashtirish ham boshlandi. Bu borada SSSR Xitoy Xalq Respublikasiga katta yordam ko'rsatdi. Uning yordami bilan 250 dan ortiq yirik sanoat korxonalarini qurildi. 1976-yil sentabrda Mao Szedun vafot etdi. Bu hodisa Xitoyda hokimiyat uchun kurashni avj oldirdi. Partiya rahbarligiga Xua G o-fen keldi.

To'rtlar to'dasi «Ishlab chiqarishga juda katta zarar keltirganlikda» ayblanib, qamoqqa olindi. Oxir-oqibatda hokimiyat tepasiga «pragmatiklar» deb atalgan guruh keldi. Bu guruhga «madaniy inqilob» yillarida qatag'on qilingan Den Syaopin rahbarlik qilar edi. Xitoy Xalq Respublikasi yangi rahbariyati Mao Szedun yo'lini xato deb e'lon qildi. «Katta sakrash» va iqtisodiyotning to'la davlat nazoratiga olinganligi davlat va xalqqa ulkan kulfat keltirganligi tan olindi va ular qoralandi. 1978-yildan pragmatiklar aralash iqtisodiyotni yoqlab chiqdilar. Davlat rahbarligida bozor iqtisodiyotiga o'tish yo'li tanlandi. Bu tarixga «iqtisodiy va siyosiy hayotni modernizatsiya qilish» nomi bilan kirdi. Chet el sarmoyasining mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga joylashtirilishi uchun qulay sharoit yaratildi. Qishloqda xalq kom munalari tarqatib yuborildi. Shirkat tuzumi bekor qilindi. Ularning o'rniga oila pudrati joriy etildi. Shu yo'l bilan aholini oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari bilan ta'minlash vazifasi hal etildi.

Sanoatda ham chuqur islohotlar o'tkazildi. Chunonchi, davlat korxonalarini xo'jalik hisobi asosida ishlaydigan bo'ldi. Kichik va o'rta tadbirkorlikka keng yo'l ochildi. Ayni paytda sanoatning maishiy tovarlar ishlab chiqaruvchi sohasini rivojlantirishga katta e'tibor berildi. Yangi siyosat o'z samarasini bermay qolmadi. 80-yillar oxiriga kelib Xitoy ko'mir, televizor, shoyi-gazlama, sement ishlab chiqarish bo'yicha dunyoda birinchi o'ringa chiqdi. Mamlakat oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari bilan o'zini o'zi ta'minlaydigan bo'ldi. Bular, o'z navbatida, aholi turmush darajasining o'sishiga olib keldi. 90-yillarda davlatda po'lat, rangli metallar eritish, sement, mineral o'g'it ishlab chiqarish, ko'p tarmoqli mashinasozlik shakllandi. To'qimachilik sanoati mahsulotlari jahon bozorini egalladi. An'anaviy hunarmandchilik: ipakdan, suyakdan badiiy buyumlar yasash, chinni mahsulotlar taniqli bo'ladi. Dengiz mahsulotlari, dorivor o'simliklar, yog'och mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish ortdi. Ishlab chiqarishda samaradorlik ko'tarildi.

1992-yildan boshlab Xitoyda iqtisodiy islohotning yangi bosqichi boshlandi. Ushbu bosqich — islohotni takomillashtirish va jadallashtirish, iqtisodiy siyosatni mafkuradan xoli qilish va rejali boshqaruvdan bozor iqtisodiyotiga izchillik bilan o'tish bosqichi, deb nom oldi. Bu bosqich ayni paytda iqtisodiyotda davlat mulki hissasining kamayib borishini ham o'z ichiga oladi.

Hatto 1998-yilda Osiyoda pul muammosi inqirozi hamda tarixda kam uchraydigan kuchli suv toshqiniga duch kelinganda ham Xitoyda ishlab chiqarishning jami qiymati 1997-yildagidan 7,8 foizga ko'tarildi. Mazkur davrda qator sanoat va qishloq xo'jalik mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish miqdori, masalan, guruch, paxta, go'sht, yog'moy, ko'mir, po'lat, sement, gazlama, televizor ishlab chiqarish bo'yicha Xitoy dunyoda birinchi o'ringa chiqdi. Davlat tashqi pul muomalasi zaxirasi 45 milliard dollarga yetdi. Xitoy oidingi iqtisodiy qoloq holatdan Amerika, Yaponiya, Germaniya, Fransiya, Angliya va Italiyadan keyin dunyoda yettinchi o'ringa chiqdi.

90-yillardan belgilangan «Sotsialistik bozor xo'jaligiga o'tish»ning mazmuni shuki, qishloq xo'jaligini tartibga solish, yerni ayrim xonadonlarning yakka xo'jalik yuritishiga asoslangan oilaviy pudrat deb atalgan usulda ishlash, dehqonlarning tomorqa uchastkalarini kengaytirish, yordamchi hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirish, ortiqcha mahsulotni bozorda dehqonning o'zi sotishi imkoniyatini yaratishni nazarda tutadi. Shaharlarda «direktiva asosida rejalashtiriladigan sohani qisqartirish», sanoat korxonalarini «mustaqil xo'jalik tashkilotlariga» aylantirish, tovar munosabatlarini rivojlantirish, «narx-navo davlat yo'li bilan bir xil belgilab qo'yiladigan sohani toraytirish», chog'roq xususiy va jamoa korxonalari, kosibchilik ustaxonalari faoliyatini, asosan xizmat ko'rsatish va savdo-sotiq xususiy korxonaga egaligini rivojlantirish, mamlakat iqtisodiga chet el sarmoyasini jalb qilish xo'jalik tizimi islohotining bosh bo'g'ini bo'ldi.

XULOSA:

Xulosa sifatida shuni aytish joizki, bozor tartibini ushlab turish, bozorning rovidan to'liq foydalanish, monopoliya va noqonuniy raqobatni cheklash, mahsulot sifatiga kafolat berish, iste'molchilarning huquq va manfaatlarini himoya qilish, patent va tovar markasini berish, turli shartnomalar tuzish, ijaraga berish, aksiya savdosi bilan shug'ullanish, chek hujjatlarini tartibga solish, uy-joy, tijorat hamda bularni buzuvchilarni qanday jazolash haqida maxsus qonunlar mavjud bo'lib, ularning bajarilishi qattiq nazorat qilinadi. Urushdan keyin Xitoy Sovet davlati bilan yaqin munosabatda bo'ldi.

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**MAHMUDXO'JA BEHBUDIYNING MILLAT G'AMIDA O'TKAZGAN
IBRATLI UMRI**

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Mahmudxo_ja Behbudiyning ilmiy va ijodiy sohada olib borgan mashaqqatli izlanishlari, millatni uyg_otish sohasida olib borgan islohotlari haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Shuningdek, millatni ma'rifatli qilish uchun ilmiy maqolalar, avomning ilmdan uzoqlashib to_y-marakalarga berilganligi va avom dastidan chekkan uqubatlari yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *faoliyat, tarix, asr, hadis, umr, yaratish, ma'rifatpatvarlik, millatni uyg_otish, ilm-ma'rifatli qilish, yo_lga qo_yish, diniy, dunyoviy, azob, ilm, to_y va marakalar, isrof, yetim, taraqqiyot, qurbon.*

Hayot faoliyati davomida dunyoning ko_p davlatida bo_lib u yurtlardagi iqtisodiy va manaviy-ma'rifiy taraqqiyotni ko_rib, tarixda butun dunyoni titratib, butun dunyoga haligacha ustozlik qilayotgan buyuk Turkistonni ma'naviy va iqtisodiy qoloqlikdan qutqarishni hayotidagi eng oliy maqsadi deb bilgan, bu yo_lda qurbon bo_lishini bilaturib jiddu-jaht bilan hech bir to_siq va qiyinchiliklarga azob-uqubatlarga e'tibor bermay ilm-ma'rifat yo_lida qurbon bo_lgan Mahmudxo_ja Behbudi juda oz atigi 45 yil umr ko_rdi. Bu oz umri davomida diniy va dunyoviy ilmlarni chuqur o_rganishga bel bog_ladi. Jahonda bo_layotgan voqea-hodisalar, jumladan, urushlar va ularning sababi, mohiyatini millat manfaati nuqtai nazaridan tafakkur chig_irig_idan o_tkazdi. Shu bilan birga tariximizning tanazzul bosqichlari, sabablarini taftish qildi.

Mahmudxo_ja Behbudi ota-onasidan erta ajralib yetim holda ulg_aygan bo_lsada 25 yoshida Muftiylik maqomiga sazovor bo_ldi. Hayotinnig qolgan qismini, maraka-marosimlariga bor-budini sarflab boylari kerilib, faqirlari qarzga botib lekin farzandi ilm olishiga, sabot chiqarib ziyoli bo_lishiga sariq chaqa sarflamagan avomning, taraqqiyotga tik boqmasdan tilidan bid'at, shirk, kufr so_zlari tushmay muqaddas islomning asl mohiyatini tushunmay zamondan g_ofil qolgan dindorlarini yo_lini to_g_irlashga sarfladi.

O_{zi} asos solgan –Oyna|| jurnalidagi maqolalarida, –Padarkush|| dramasida va ko_{plab} asarlarida, ularni noto_{g_{ri}} yo_{lda} ekanini amaliy va nazariy, diniy-dunyoviy ilmlar asosida isbotlab, ajoyib uslubda keng yoritib berdi. Ammo bunday sharaflil xizmatlarni ilmsiz, johil avom qadriga yetmadi. Behbudiyga ayovsiz aziyat yetqazishdi.

Behbudiy ana shunday millat muammosini ta'kidlab bir maqolasida shunday yozadi; –Endi a'molimizg_a diqqat qilmoq kerak. Aksar xalqi- mizni a'moli shulki, ishlasa va foyda qilsa. Shoyadki, o_{g_{il}} va qizini to_y qilsa va ham qanday! O_z qatorindagi odamlarni qilgan to_yidan ziyodaroq! Bechora kosibni a'moli to_ydur. O_{zi} rohat yuzi ko_rmaydur. Kecha-kunduzni 18, balki 20 soatni mehnatg_a o_tkaraturgon kosiblarimiz bordur. Haqqincha yemaydur, kiymaydur. O_n va yigirma sanalar mehnat va mashaqqat etar va xudodan o_{g_{il}} tilar, to_y qilmoq uchun. Ana, bechorani a'moli. Yigirma sanalik meqnati uch kun to_yda tamom. Yana Ahmad porina qavli va xona girad. To_y musrifi uchun qarz egalaridan qochadur. Katta to_y qilib xotun olgon bir qism bechoralarni holig_a yig_{lamoq} kerak. Uch kunlik to_yni azosi ba'zi oilalarda o_n yil, hatto, bir umr surar, balki bevatan va xonavayronlikg_a sabab bo_{lur}. Bir kosibni akdu nikohig_a, to_{yu} obro_{sig_a} ming so_m. Bir o_{rt}ahol uchun 2000 yo 3000 so_m. Nimboy uchun to_{rt}-besh ming so_m kerak. Bu so_mlarni yuzdan yetmish beshi yeyilib-ichilib... ketar. Bu so_mlar aslinda kimniki edi? Bonka, firma, foydaxo_r- niki. Tabiiy, bularg_a pullarini bermoqlozim, na beri- lur? Bog_u xona va uyi ichindagi asbobni sotib bermoq kerak. Bechora kelin va kuyovni ko_{rpa} va libosig_{acha} sotilur, qarzxohg_a berilur|| . Behbudiy XIX-asrning ikkinchi yarmida o_z maqolalarida muammo sifatida tahlil qilgan bu kabi odatlar bugungi kunimizning ham dolzarb masalalaridan biri bo_{lib} qolmoqda.

Behbudiy nazarida ma'rifat uchun birgina maktab kifoya qilmasdi. Zamon va dunyo voqealari bilan tanishib bormoq, millat va Vatanning kundalik hayotidan, ahvolidan, ogoh bo'lm_{oq} kerak edi. Binobarin, millat uchun shunday oyna kerak ediki, unda u o'z qabohatini ham, malohatini ham ko'ra olsun. Mana shu ehtiyoj va zarurat Behbudiyini teatr va matbuot sari boshladi. –Padarkush|| shu tariqa maydonga keldi., 1911-yilda yozilgan –Padarkush|| dramasi 1913-yildagina bosilib chiqadi. Kitob jildidagi «Borodino jangi va Rusiyaning fransuzlar bosqinidan xalos bo'lishining yubiley sanasiga bag'ishlanadi», degan yozuv va uning Tiflis senzurasining ruxsati bilan chop etilishi shuni ko'rsatadiki, ish oson ko'chmagan. Pyesa bosilib chiqqandan keyin ham uni sahnaga qo'yish uchun yaqin bir yil vaqt ketdi. Muallif bu haqdagi xatlarga javoban kinoyaomuz: –Turkistonda bekor odam yo'qki, xalq uchun ishlasa. Bekor kishi yo'qki, teatru sahnasiga chiqib, –masxarabozlik|| qilsa||, deb yozgan edi.

Behbudiy ana shunday keng fikr sohibi va zamonasida haqiqatni ochiq-oydin ayta oladigan o'z zamonasining ma'rifatparvari edi. Bu zotning asriy orzu umidlari hozirda yangi O'zbekistonda amalga oshib bormoqda va allomaning buyuk xizmatlar qalbimizda mangu qolajak.

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**IQLIM O'ZGARISHLARI MUAMMO VA OQIBATLARI. IQLIM
O'ZGARISHIGA QARSHI KURASH. IQLIM O'ZGARISHI VA INSONIYAT.
IQLIM O'ZGARISHI SABABLARI.**

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(Surxondaryo, Termiz)

Anotatsiya: *Iqlim o'zgarishida insoniyatning ta'siri, iqlim o'zgarishi sabablari, Iqlim o'zgarishi sayyoramizga halokatli ta'siri, Osiyoda iqlim o'zgarishining ta'siri*

Kalit so'zlar: *Iqlim, ornitolog, sayyora, quyosh, yer, BMT, ekotizimlar Iqlim o'zgarishi muammolari*

Sanoat rivojlanishi oqibatida atmosferaga chiqayotgan uglevodorod gazi miqdori yil sayin ko'paymoqda. Bu esa sayyoramizda —bug_xona hodisasi—ni kuchaytirib, keskin iqlim o'zgarishlarini yuzaga keltiryapti. Oqibatda tabiiy ofatlar ko'paymoqda. Dunyoning ko'pgina mintaqalarida tabiiy muvozanat buzilmoqda: ayrim joylarda yog'ingarchilik odatdagidan ancha ko'p bo'lsa, boshqa hududlarda qurg'oqchilik avj olyapti. Joriy yilning o'zida kuzatilgan —tabiiy me'yorlarning buzilish|| holatlari bunga yaqqol misol bo'ladi. 2010 yil bahorida ba'zi Yevropa davlatlarida kuchli suv toshqinlari ro'y berdi, yoz esa juda issiq va quruq keldi.

Jahon meteorologiya tashkiloti rahbari Mishel Jarroning fikricha, sayyoramizda o'rtacha harorat 7 darajaga ko'tarilsa, Yer yuzi hududining teng yarmi hayot uchun yaroqsiz bo'lib qoladi. Chunki ayrim unumdor yerlar cho'llanishga yuz tutsa, ayrimlari suv ostida qoladi.

Iqlim o'zgarishlari hayvonot olamiga ham katta ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Ornitologlarning kuzatuvlariga qaraganda, global isish tufayli Hindistonda yashovchi uzundumli to'ntalar shimoliy o'lkalarga ko'cha boshlagan. Olimlarning fikricha, ellik yildan keyin mintaqamizda uzundumli to'ntalar qarg'alarga nisbatan ko'payar ekan.

Butun dunyoni xavotirga solayotgan global iqlim o'zgarishining oqibatlari Yevropada yaqqol sezilmoqda. Masalan, bahorda yoqqan tinimsiz yomg'ir keltirib

chiqargan toshqinlar bir necha shaharni vayron qildi. May oyida havo harorati so_nggi 250 yildagi eng yuqori ko_rsatkichga chiqdi. Buning oqibatida Italiya va Shveysariyadagi muzliklar maydoni keskin qisqara boshladi. Mutaxassislarning ta'kidlashicha, iqlim o_zgarishi sababli tog_larda o_pirilishlar, daryo o_zanlarining o_zgarishi, landshaftlarning buzilishi ro_y bermoqda.

Osiyoda ham iqlim o_zgarishining belgilari kuzatildi. Iyul-avgust oylarida Bangladesh va Pokistonda yoqqan tinimsiz yomg_ir oqibatida millionlab odamlar boshpanasiz qoldi.

Hisob-kitoblarga ko_ra, har yili atmosferaga 100 million tonnadan ortiq uglevodorod chiqarilar ekan. Shuning 74 foizi rivojlangan davlatlar hissasiga to_g_ri keladi. Olimlarning fikricha, o_rmon yong_inlari oqibatida atmosferaga chiqayotgan karbonad kislotasi sanoat chiqindilarining 50 foiziga teng ekan. Havoga ko_tarilgan tutun atmosferaning yuqori qatlamida kuyindi zarralarini ko_paytiradi. Oqibatda, sayyoramizga Quyoshdan kelayotgan issiqlik energiyasi qaytadan koinotga yoyilish o_rniga, Yerning o_zida qolib, –bug_xona hodisasi–ni keltirib chiqarmoqda. Jahon hamjamiyati global isishga qarshi qator chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirmoqda. 1997 yili sayyoramizda iqlim o_zgarishining oldini olishda hamkorlik maqsadida Kioto protokoli imzolandi. 2005 yildan kuchga kirgan bu hujjat atmosferaga chiqarilayotgan zararli gazlar miqdorini bosqichma-bosqich kamaytirib borishni ko_zda tutadi. Lekin bu maqsadlarga erishish oson bo_lmayotir. Chunki zararli gazlarni kamaytirish uchun ularni chiqarayotgan sanoat korxonalarini faoliyatini to_xtashga to_g_ri keladi. Bu esa daromaddan voz kechish, ishsizlik muammosini kuchaytirish, demakdir. Shu bois qator davlatlar Kioto protokoli talablarini bajarish masalasiga sovuqqonlik bilan qaramoqda.

BMT tashabbusi bilan Meksikaning Kankun shahrida global isish muammolariga bag_ishlangan xalqaro konferensiya bo_lib o_tganligi. sayyoramizda tabiiy muvozanatni tiklash borasidagi ishlar to_xtab qolmaganining isboti desak adashmaymiz. Unda 193 davlatdan 25 ming vakil qatnashmoqda. Konferensiyada tashvish bilan tilga olingan fikr shu bo_ldiki, dunyoda o_rtacha harorat 2–3 foiz ko_tarilgan va bu o_ta tahlikali holdir. Anjuman qatnashchilari barcha davlatlarni, birinchi navbatda, rivojlangan mamlakatlarni tabiiy muvozanatni tiklash yo_lida sarf-xarajatlardan chekinmaslikka da'vat qildi. Ularning fikricha, rivojlangan mamlakatlar –uchinchi dunyo|| davlatlariga yangi texnologiyalarni taqdim etishi, ekologik toza ishlab chiqarishni yo_lga qo_yishga qaratilgan loyihalarni moliyalashtirishi maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining Iqlim o'zgarishi to'g'risidagi konventsiyasiga (UNFCCC) ko'ra, iqlim o'zgarishi - bu global atmosferaning tarkibini o'zgartiradigan va Yerda tabiiy ravishda sodir bo'ladigan muntazam

o'zgarishlarni ko'paytiradigan inson faoliyati bilan bevosita yoki bilvosita bog'liq bo'lgan iqlim o'zgarishi. sayyora

Erda vaqti -vaqti bilan sodir bo'ladigan tabiiy tsikllar mavjud, shu jumladan iqlim o'zgarishi. Masalan, taxminan 10.000 XNUMX yil oldin, sayyoramizning iqlimi hozirgigidan sovuqroq ediva muzliklar er yuzining katta qismini egallagan; asta -sekin o'zgarishlar oxirgi muzlik davri bilan tugadi.

Iqlim o'zgarishi sayyoramizga halokatli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Buning oqibatlarini chastotada ham, intensivlikda ham ortib bormoqda issiqxona ta'sirining ko'payishi.

Yer tarixida bir necha iqlim o'zgarishlari bo'lgan, ammo inson tomonidan ishlab chiqarilgan bu eng qizg'in. Uning asosiy sababi atmosferaga atmosferaga chiqaradigan sanoat, qishloq xo'jaligi, transport faoliyati va boshqalar. Biroq, iqlim o'zgarishi barcha mamlakatlarga bir xil ta'sir qilmaydi chunki u ekotizimlarning xususiyatlariga va har bir issiqxona gazining issiqlikni ushlab turish qobiliyatiga qarab ishlaydi.

Iqlim o'zgarishi turli xil ta'sirga ega bo'lib, ular quyidagilarga ta'sir qiladi:

Ekotizimlar: Iqlim o'zgarishi ekotizimlarga hujum qiladi, biologik xilma-xillikni kamaytiradi va ko'plab turlarning yashashini qiyinlashtiradi. Shuningdek, u tsikldagi uglerod zaxirasini o'zgartiradi va har bir turning yashash joylarini parchalaydi. Parchalangan yashash joylari - bu hayvonlar va o'simliklar duch keladigan katta xavf va ba'zida bu turning yo'q bo'lib ketishini anglatishi mumkin.

Inson tizimlari: Atmosfera, yog'ingarchilik, harorat va boshqalarga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi sababli. Iqlim o'zgarishi inson tizimiga hujum qiladi, qishloq xo'jaligida ishlash samaradorligini yo'qotadi. Masalan, ko'plab ekinlar haddan tashqari qurg'oqchilik tufayli zarar ko'radi yoki yuqori harorat tufayli etishtirilmaydi, almashlab ekish kerak, zararkunandalar ko'payadi va hokazo. Boshqa tomondan, qurg'oqchilik sug'orish, shaharlarni etkazib berish, ko'chalarni yuvish, bezak, sanoat va hokazolar uchun ichimlik suvi etishmovchiligini kuchaytiradi. Va xuddi shu sababli, bu sog'liqqa zarar etkazadi, yangi kasalliklar paydo bo'ladi ...

Shahar tizimlari: Iqlim o'zgarishi, shuningdek, transport tizimlari yoki yo'nalishlarini o'zgartirishga olib keladigan shahar tizimlariga ta'sir qiladi, yangi texnologiyalarni takomillashtirish yoki binolarga o'rnatish kerak va umuman hayot tarziga ta'sir qiladi

Iqtisodiy tizimlar: Iqtisodiy tizimlar haqida nima deyish mumkin. Shubhasiz, iqlim o'zgarishi energiya olish, ishlab chiqarish, tabiiy kapitaldan foydalanadigan tarmoqlarga ta'sir qiladi ...

Ijtimoiy tizimlar: Iqlim o'zgarishi ijtimoiy tizimlarga ham ta'sir qiladi, migratsiya o'zgarishini keltirib chiqaradi, urushlar va mojarolarga olib keladi, tenglikni buzadi va hokazo.

Afrikadagi iqlim o'zgarishining oqibatlari

Afrika iqlim o'zgarishiga eng zaif qit'alardan biridir. Afrikaning aksariyat qismida kam yog'ingarchilik bo'ladi, faqat markaziy va sharqiy mintaqalarda yog'ingarchilik ko'paymoqda. Taxminlarga ko'ra Afrikada quruq va yarim quruq erlarning ko'payishi kuzatiladi 5 yilgacha 8% dan 2080% gacha. Qurg'oqchilik va ob-havoning o'zgarishi oqibatida suv tanqisligi tufayli odamlar suvni ko'paytirmoqda. Bu qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishiga zarar etkazadi va oziq-ovqat mahsulotlaridan foydalanish tobora qiyinlashib boradi.

Boshqa tomondan, dengiz sathining ko'tarilishi Iskandariya, Qohira, Lome, Kotonu, Lagos va Massava kabi past qirg'oq mintaqalarida joylashgan yirik shaharlarga ta'sir qiladi.

Osiyoda iqlim o'zgarishining ta'siri

Afrikadan boshqa ta'sirlar Osiyoda ko'rinadi. Masalan, muzliklarning erishi toshqinlar va tosh ko'chkilarining ko'payishiga olib keladi va Tibet, Hindiston va Bangladesh suv resurslariga ta'sir qiladi; Bu o'z navbatida daryolar oqimining pasayishiga va muzliklarning pasayishiga qarab chuchuk suvning mavjudligiga sabab bo'ladi. 2050 yilda, 1000 milliarddan ortiq odam suv tanqisligidan aziyat chekishi mumkin. Janubi-Sharqiy Osiyo va ayniqsa, haddan tashqari ko'p bo'lgan yirik deltalar mintaqalari toshqin xavfi ostida. Kelgusi 30 yil ichida Osiyodagi turli xil bosim va iqlim o'zgarishlari sababli 30 foizga yaqin marjon riflari yo'q bo'lib ketishi kutilmoqda. Yomg'irning o'zgarishi diareya kasalliklarining ko'payishiga olib keladi, asosan toshqin va qurg'oqchilik bilan bog'liq.

Shuningdek, u bezgak chivinlari sonini ko'paytirishi va shu bilan ko'proq Osiyo populyatsiyasiga ta'sir qilishi mumkin.

Lotin Amerikasidagi oqibatlar Ushbu sohadagi muzliklarning orqaga chekinishi va natijada yog'ingarchilikning pasayishi qishloq xo'jaligi, iste'mol va energiya ishlab chiqarish uchun mavjud suvning kamayishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Mavjud suv tanqisligi bilan oziq-ovqat ekinlarining hosildorligi ham pasayadi va bu oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi muammolariga olib keladi.

Ko'pgina tropik mintaqalarning yo'q bo'lib ketishi tufayli Lotin Amerikasi biologik xilma-xillikni sezilarli darajada yo'qotishi mumkin. Tuproq namligining pasayishi a sabab bo'lishi kutilmoqda tropik o'rmonlarni sharqiy Amazoniyada savannalar bilan asta-sekin almashtirish. Karib dengizida joylashgan yana bir yo'qolib ketish xavfi ostida bo'lgan ekotizim - bu ko'plab jonli dengiz resurslari

joylashgan mercan riflari. Dengiz sathining ko'tarilishi pasttekis mintaqalarda, ayniqsa Karib dengizida toshqin xavfini oshiradi.

Xulosa; iqlim o'zgarishi va global isish Iqlim o'zgarishi va global isish o'rtasidagi farqni xulosa qilib aytganda, iqlim o'zgarishi - bu Yer sharining yoki mintaqaning uzoq vaqt davomida o'zgarishi, global isish esa Yerning o'rtacha haroratining ko'tarilishi. Darhaqiqat, global isish ba'zi hollarda iqlim o'zgarishiga olib keladi, chunki haroratning oshishi yog'ingarchilikning ko'payishiga olib keladi va ma'lum bir mintaqadagi eng past va eng yuqori haroratni o'zgartiradi. Odamlarning aralashuvi - tezlashadigan umumiy omil, chunki havo ifloslanishi global isishga ham, iqlim o'zgarishiga ham yordam beradi. Bundan tashqari, ikkalasi ham er yuzidagi har bir tirik organizm uchun tahdidir, chunki tez o'zgarib turadigan ob -havo sharoiti ko'plab hayvonlarga salbiy ta'sir qiladi va ko'plab noyob turlar Yer yuzidan yo'qolib bormoqda. Shuning uchun Yerda hayotni saqlab qolish uchun darhol keskin harakatlarni amalga oshirish kerak.

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БОЛЕЗНИ ЛИСТЬЕВ ЧЕРЕШНИ И ВИШНИ ВЫЗЫВАЮЩИЕ МИКРОМИЦЕТАМИ

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Аннотация: По данным литературы на листьях черешни и вишни зарегистрированы болезни, которые вызывают более 60 видов грибов. Среди них имеются такие важные с экономической точки зрения болезни, как клястероспориоз, ожог листьев, млечный блеск листьев, коккомикоз и полистигмоз. Ряд других болезней черешни и вишни имеет ограниченное распространение и не имеет экономического значения. У довольно большого числа грибов, зарегистрированных на или выделенных из листьев таксономия неясна, и патогенность их к растениям-хозяевам не подтверждена экспериментально. В данной статье приведены результаты критического анализа всех видов грибов, о встречаемости которых на листьях черешни и вишни сообщалась в мировой литературе.

Ключевые слова: черешня, вишня, листья, грибы, болезни, пятнистость.

Возделыванию деревьев черешни, вишни и повышению урожайности их фруктов оказывают неблагоприятное воздействие ряд фитопатогенных грибов (и других микроорганизмов), которые вызывают преждевременное опадение листьев, поражают также побеги, ветви, плоды, сильно ослабляют деревья, из-за чего они становятся неустойчивыми к зимним холодам, и у них сильно снижается урожай в последующих сезонах. Примерами таких болезней могут быть широко распространённые в нашей стране клястероспориоз, монилиоз и отсутствующий в Узбекистане коккомикоз.

В данном обзоре приводится основная информация о всех видах фитопатогенных микромицетов, которые обнаружены во всех старнах мира, с критическим анализом приведённых разными авторами данных.

В тексте латинские названия грибов – возбудители болезней черешни и вишни приведены в алфавитном порядке, их таксономическое положение (филум, порядок, семейство) – по Alexopoulos et al. [1], материалам базы данных Wikipedia и Mucobank (2021), географическое распространение

патогенов – по данным Компендиума [2], международных организаций CABI (Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International), EPPO (European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization) и публикациям в литературе.

Apiognomonina erythrostoma (Pers.) v. Höhnelt, син. *Gnomonia erythrostoma* (Pers.) Auersw., *Ascochyta effusa* Lib., *Ascochyta stipata* Lib., *Libertina stipata* (Lib.) Hahn., *Septoria effusa* (Lib.) Desm., *Phomopsis stipata* (Lib.) Sutton, *Septoria pallescens* Sacc. **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, Diaporthales, Gnomoniaceae. **Поражаемые виды:** вишня, черешня, абрикос. **Вызываемая болезнь:** ожог листьев вишни (Cherry leaf scorch). **Вредоносность:** имеет экономическое значение. В отдалённых странах (напр., в Италии в 2006 г.) на определённых сортах косточковых культур вызвал раннее опадение листьев и значительные потери урожая. **Географическое распространение:** Болезнь распространена в основном в Европе; есть неподтверждённые сообщения о нахождении патогена в Азии – в Китае, Японии и Южной Корее [2, 3-5]. В Узбекистане отсутствует. **Примечание:** Подробные сведения о симптомах болезни, цикле развития, микроморфологии гриба-возбудителя и мерах борьбы приведены в литературе [5].

Blumeriella jaapii (Rehm) Arx, син. *Coccomyces hiemalis* Higgins и др., *Phloeosporella padi* (Lib.) Arx, *Cylindrosporium padi* P. Karst. ex Sacc. и др. **Примечание 1:** бинomial *Coccomyces pruni-tomentosi* Miura, приводимый в качестве возбудителя коккомикоза на вишне обыкновенной и войлочной на Дальнем Востоке [5] является сомнительным таксоном (Incertae sedis) и данные о нём в базах данных Интернета отсутствуют. **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, Helotiales, Dermataceae. **Поражаемые виды:** вишня, реже – черешня и слива, декоративные и дикие виды рода *Prunus*. **Вызываемая болезнь:** «коккомикоз вишни» (cherry leaf spot). **Вредоносность:** считается экономически важным заболеванием вишни и черешни; во влажные сезоны вызывает раннее опадение листьев в середине лета, из-за чего деревья сильно ослабевают, плодовые почки зимой погибают, снижается урожай следующего года. **Географическое распространение:** Европа (25 стран, в том числе Россия, Украина, Беларусь, Литва), Азия (Азербайджан, Бутан, Грузия, Китай, Пакистан, Турция), Сев. Америка (Канада, США). В Узбекистане отсутствует. **Примечание 2:** поражаются болезнью взрослые деревья в садах и саженцы в питомниках [2,]. Более подробные сведения о болезни и её возбудителе имеются в литературе [11].

Cercospora circumscissa Sacc., син. *Cercospora cerasella* Sacc., *Passalora circumscissa* (Sacc.) U. Braun, *Pseudocercospora circumscissa* (Sacc.) Y.L. Guo, телеоморфа *Mycosphaerella cerasella* Aderhold. **Таксономическое положение:**

Ascomycota, Capnodiales, Mycosphaerellaceae. **Поражаемые виды:** вишня, черешня; есть также сведения о поражении листьев миндаля, тёрна, сливы и персика. **Вызываемая болезнь:** церкоспороз, пятнистость листьев (*Cercospora leaf spot*). **Вредоносность:** Обычно встречается вместе с коккомикозом, клястероспориозом, мучнистой росой и против них применяются общие меры борьбы. **Географическое распространение:** Европа (Германия, Италия, Литва, Франция, Сербия, бывший СССР и др.), Азия (Израиль), США [2,4]. В Узбекистане отсутствует.

Chondrostereum purpureum (Pers.: Fr.) Poulaz, син. *Stereum purpureum* Pers.: Fr. **Таксономическое положение:** Basidiomycota, Agaricales, Cyphellaceae (раньше – Russulales, Stereaceae). **Поражаемые виды:** виды рода *Prunus*, черешня, алыча, слива, реже – яблоня, груша, ягодники, многие виды декоративных и лесных широколистных, а иногда и хвойных деревьев. **Вызываемая болезнь:** «млечный блеск» – серебристость листьев на поражённых ветвях (*Silver leaf disease*), гниль ветвей и стволов. **Вредоносность:** болезнь может привести косточковые плодовые деревья к гибели. Имеет важное экономическое значение во Франции, Австралии, Новой Зеландии, Чили и других странах.

Dermea cerasi (Pers.) Fr., син. *Dermatella prunastri* Dowson, *Cenangium prunastri* (Pers.) Fr. **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, Helotiales, Dermataceae. **Поражаемые виды:** вишня обыкновенная и американская чёрная (дикая), слива, абрикос. **ВБ:** пятнистость листьев, слабый патоген или сапрофит (*Leaf spot, saprobe on dry leaves*). **Вредоносность:** не вредоносна. **Географическое распространение:** Великобритания, Россия (Дальний Восток), США (Аляска), Австралия.

Didymella pomorum (Thüm.) Q. Chen & L. Cai, син. *Phoma pomorum* Thüm., *Peyronellaea pomorum* var. *pomorum* (Thüm.) Aveskamp et al., *Peyronellaea pruni-avium* (Allesch) Goid. (nom. nud.), *Phoma triticina* E. Müll., *Coniothyrium prunicola* (Opiz ex Sacc.) Husz., *Phyllosticta pruni-avii* Allesch., *Phyllosticta prunicola* Sacc., *Phyllosticta prunicola* var. *pruni-spinosae* (Allesch.) Allesch., *Phyllostictella pruni-spinosae* (Allesch.) Tassi, *Phyllosticta pruni-nanae* Săvulescu & Sandu, *Phyllosticta pruni-spinosae* Allesch., *Phyllosticta pyrina* (Sacc.) Goid., *Sphaceloma prunicola* (Sacc.) Jenkins и др. **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, Diaporthales, Didymellaceae. **Поражаемые виды:** вишня, черешня, слива, абрикос, персик, яблоня, лавровишня – Нана||. Выделялся из соломины пшеницы и некоторых двудольных растений. **Вызываемая болезнь:** пятнистость листьев, побегов, плодов (*Shot-hole spot, leaf, shoot and fruit spot*). **Вредоносность:** болезнь считают важной в Венгрии, Грузии и некоторых странах Балканского

полуострова [1]. **Географическое распространение:** Венгрия, Литва, Сербия, Нидерланды, Швейцария, Россия (Дальний Восток), Грузия, Индия, ЮАР, Австралия [3,4]. **Примечание.** У анаморфы этого вида выделяют самостоятельную разновидность *Phoma pomorum* var. *potorum* Thüm., син. *Phyllosticta prunicola* Opiz ex Sacc., *Phyllosticta prunicola* Sacc., которая вызывает пятнистость листьев на черешне и сливе [3,4].

Discosia artocreas (Tode) Fr., син. *Sphaeria artocreas* Tode. **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, порядок неизвестен (Incertae sedis), Sporocadaceae. Гриб встречается только в конидиальной стадии, телеоморфа неизвестна. **Поражаемые виды:** вишня, слива и другие виды деревьев; первоначально выделен из мёртвых листьев бука. **Вызываемая болезнь:** пятнистость листьев, слабый патоген, сапрофит (Leaf spot, weak parasite, saprobe). **Вредоносность:** мало вредоносна. **Географическое распространение:** Германия, Россия (Дальний Восток).

Monilia kusanoi P. Henn., телеоморфа *Monilinia kusanoi* (Takahashi) Yamamoto. **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, Helotiales, Sclerotiniaceae. **Поражаемые виды:** вишня, черешня, абрикос японский, декоративные виды вишни. **Вызываемая болезнь:** гниль листьев, цветов и плодов (Monilia leaf blight and green fruit rot). **Вредоносность:** мало вредоносна. **Географическое распространение:** Япония, Корея. В Узбекистане отсутствует.

Phyllosticta circumscissa Cooke. **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, Botryosphaeriales Botryosphaeriaceae. **Поражаемые виды:** черешня, абрикос и др. косточковые культуры. **Вызываемая болезнь:** пятнистость листьев (Leaf spot). **Вредоносность:** нет сведений. **Географическое распространение:** Великобритания, США, Канада, Южная Австралия [16, 22]. В Узбекистане отсутствует.

Phyllosticta persicae Sacc. **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, Botryosphaeriales, Botryosphaeriaceae. **Поражаемые виды:** косточковые фруктовые деревья. **Вызываемая болезнь:** пятнистость листьев (Target leaf spot). **Вредоносность:** нет сведений.

Другие виды рода *Phyllosticta*. Кроме двух приведённых выше видов в литературе описаны ещё 10 видов рода *Phyllosticta*, вызывающие пятнистости листьев на косточковых культурах. О вредоносности этих видов в литературе сведений нет.

Polystigma rubrum (Pers.) DC. (невалидный вариант названия: *Polystigma rubrum* (Pers.) Wint.), анаморфа *Polystigmina rubra* (Pers.) Sacc. **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, Phyllachorales, Phyllachoraceae. **Поражаемые виды:** тёрн, алыча ферганская (слива согдская), алыча туркменская, слива, реже –

черешня, тернослива и др. фруктовые деревья (монофаг на видах рода *Prunus*). **Вызываемая болезнь:** полистигмоз, красная пятнистость (Red leaf spot, blackthorn dotty). **Вредоносность:** в Южной Европе и на Среднем Востоке считается важной болезнью. **Географическое распространение:** Бельгия, Болгария, Великобритания, Венгрия, Германия, Молдавия, Сербия, Украина, Ирак, Иран, Турция, Узбекистан и др. центрoазиатские страны.

Виды рода *Septoria*. Таксономическое положение: Ascomycota, Carpodiales, Mycosphaerellaceae. По собранным авторами данным на косточковых культурах пятнистость (септориоз) вызывают три вида: *Septoria amygdali* Woronich. на миндале в бывшем СССР, *Septoria cerasi* Pass. на листьях вишни в Западной Европе, в Литве [4] и в Узбекистане в Ферганской долине на вишне-антипке магалевской, и *Septoria pruni* Ellis в США.

S. amygdali является сомнительным видом (*Incertae sedis*) и о нём в базах данных интернета сведений нет. Два остальных вида признаны в виде легальных таксонов, однако какой-либо информации об их биологии и значении в интернете нам не встретилось и эти виды не включены в последние обзоры по грибам рода *Septoria* и сем. Mycosphaerellaceae.

***Stigmina carpophila* (Lév.) M.B. Ellis, син. *Clasterosporium carpophilum* Aderh., *Wilsonomyces carpophilus* (Lév) Adaskaveg, Ogawa et E. E. Butler, *Coryneum beyerinckii* Oud. (или *Coryneum beijerinckii* Oud.), *Thyrostroma carpophilum* (Lév.) B. Sutton и др.** **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, Dothideales, семейство неизвестно (*Incertae sedis*). **Поражаемые виды:** все косточковые плодовые деревья и миндаль; монофаг на видах рода *Prunus*. **Вызываемая болезнь:** клястероспориоз, дырчатая пятнистость листьев (Shot hole), язвы на побегах, ветвях и плодах. **Вредоносность:** повсеместно имеет большое экономическое значение. **Географическое распространение:** космополит.

Виды рода *Taphrina*. Таксономическое положение: Ascomycota, Taphrinales, Taphrinaceae. **Поражаемые виды:** вишня обыкновенная, горькая, мелкоплодная, американские дикие вишни, черешня, миндаль и другие косточковые плодовые деревья. **Вызываемая болезнь:** скручивание листьев, «ведьмины метлы» (Leaf curl, witches' broom). **Вредоносность:** некоторые виды имеют значение на вишне и черешне, вызывая на них ведьмины листья; другие виды важны как паразиты декоративных видов вишни в Японии. *Taphrina deformans* (Burk.) Tul., возбудитель скручивания листьев, во многих регионах мира, включая Узбекистан, имеет очень большое экономическое значение на деревьях персика. **Географическое распространение:** паразитирующие на культурных косточковых деревьях виды рода *Taphrina* космополиты, ареал ряда

других видов, поражающих, в основном дикорастущие виды вишни, ограничен Сев. Америкой [3].

Venturia cerasi Aderhold, син. *Acrosporium cerasi* Rabenh., *Fusicladium cerasi* (Rabenh.) Erikss., *Fusicladium cerasi* (Rabenh.) Aderhold, *Cladosporium cerasi* (Rabenh.) Aderhold. **Таксономическое положение:** Ascomycota, Pleosporales, Venturiaceae.

Поражаемые виды: вишня, слива, мирабель, миндаль, редко – черешня.

Вызываемая болезнь: парша вишни (пятнистость листьев и ветвей, парша плодов) (Cherry scab). **Вредоносность:** вероятно, сильное развитие болезни

может привести к снижению урожая; данных литературы о конкретных величинах потерь урожая от болезни авторы не встретили. **Географическое**

распространение: Северная Европа, Германия, Швейцария, бывший СССР, Иран, Канада, США, Бразилия, Новая Зеландия [3, 4]. В Узбекистане отсутствует.

Другие виды. Кроме приведённых выше микромицетов, листья вишни и черешни поражаются и другими грибами – возбудителями ржавчины, мучнистой росы, а также бактериями (*Erwinia amylovora* (Burrill) Winslow et al., *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *syringae* van Hall, *Pseudomonas syringae* van Hall pv. *morsprunorum* (Wormald) Young et al., *Xanthomonas arboricola* pv. *pruni* (Smith) Vauterine et al., *Xylella fastidiosa* Wells, Raju, Hung, Weisburg, Parl & Beemer), фитоплазмами (European stone fruit yellows – ESFY) и некоторыми вирусами (Cherry leaf roll virus, Cherry mottle leaf virus, Cherry rasp leaf virus, Cucumber mosaic virus) [2, 5 и др.].

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КУНДАЛИК ОДАТЛАРИМИЗНИНГ ХАЁТДАГИ ЎРНИ

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Анджон шаҳар 1- сўн БМСМ хор дирижёрлиги бўлим ўқитувчиси

Аннотация: *Инсонлар ҳаётлари давомида ўзлари истагандек турмуш тарзини юрита олиши мумкинлиги ва бунинг учун фақатгина ўзларидаги омадсизликларига сабаб бўлаётган одатларини ўзгартириш устида иш олиб борсалар ва бунда кўникмалар ҳосил қила оласалар бас.*

Калит сўзлар: *Одатлар, ҳаёт, ютуқ, мақсад.*

Аннотация: *Люди могут жить так, как они хотят, и только если они будут работать над изменением привычек, которые приводят к неудачам, и если они будут развивать необходимые для этого навыки.*

Ключевые слова: *Привычки, жизнь, достижение, цель*

Annotation: *People can live the way they want to live the life they want, and only if they work to change the habits that cause them to fail, and if they develop the skills to do so.*

Key words: *Habits, life, achievement, goal*

Жуда кўп инсонлар яъни 95 % инсонлар кунда одатланган ишини қилиш билан иш кунини бошлайди ва шу тарзда яшашга одатланган. Тадқиқотлар шуни кўрсатиб ўтдики ютуқга эриша олган инсонларда кунда бажариладигон одатлари яхши, ютуқга эришаолмаган инсонларнинг кунда бажариладигон одатлари эса яхши одатлар эмас. Ҳеч қайси инсон ўз яхши ва ё мон одатлари билан дунёга келмайди бу одатлар умримиз давомида ўзи шакиллиниб боради. Одатлар аслида ўзи нима бу ўзимиз ўйламаган холда реакция берадигон бажарадигон ишлар булар худди эрталаб тиш ювиш одати, нон ушта қилиш ва хоказо, айнан шу кўзга кўринмас одатларимиз жуда кўп нарсаларни хал эта олади. Айнан шу одатларни ота-онамиздан ўрганганмиз яъни ҳаёт тарзимиздан келиб чиққан холда одатларимиз шакиллинади. Фарзандларимизни ҳам ҳаёт тарзларини ўзгартириш ва уларни келажакларини ёрқинроқ, яхшироқ бўлиш мумкинлиги ҳақида ўйлаб кўрганмисизлар.

Болаларни ёрқин давриданок уларни камчиликларини гапирмасдан кимгадур тақлид қилиши кераклигини айтмасдан фарзандларимиз эришаётган ютуқларни рағбатлантириб туриш лозимлиги ва кимларнидур фиклари учун эмас ишдан завқ олиб ишлашлари тўғрисида тушунчалар бериш лозим, шунда фарзандлар у ишни ёрқин ки бу ишни қилсам бошлиқларга

ё ки ўқитувчимга ё қаман эмас, балки бировларни фикрига суяниб иш қилишни олди олинади ва қилаё тган иши биричи ўринда ўзини қониктириши кераклиги мақсад қилиб қўйилади. Иш фаолиятида, оилада, бизнесда ютуқга эриша олишни йўлларида бири хаё тимиз давомида бажараё тган одатларимизни ўзимиз бошқара олишимиз мумкунлиги бизни ўзимиздан чиқарувчи омилларга, инсонларга этибор қилмаслик ва бу реакцияни тўхтатиш ўзимизни қўлимизда эканлиги ва шуни бажаролган инсон шахс сифатида ўса бошлайди. Аристотел айтганидек инсонлар хаё тида бўлаё тган яхши ва нохушликлар уларнинг одатларидан келиб чиқиши сабаб бўлади деган. Бу ишларни ўзгартириш инсоннинг ўз қўлидалиги ва одатларини ўзи ўзгартира олиши мумкин. Одатда инсонлар ўзларидаги ё мин омилларга сабаб бўлаё тган одатларини, бажарадигон ишларини яхши одатларга айлантиришда кўпрок бир нечта омиллар тўсқинлик қилади булар (Зона комфорта) яъни яшаё тган шароитни ўзгартирмаслик хотиржамлик, янгиликдан қўрқиш, олаё тган маошига ўз шароитини мослаш холбуки бундан ортиғини хохлайди лекин қўрқади унга шунодоқ яшаша қулайроқ. Инсонларнинг 80 % шундай яшашга одатланган. Ютуқга эришганларнинг иш фаолиятининг мохияти нимада? улар ўзларига катта, қийин эришиши осон бўлмага мақсадлар қўяди олдига ва ўзларининг (Зона комфорта) яъни хотиржамлик шароитидан кечадилар ва чиқадилар.

Кейинги омил инсонлар ўзларини кучсиз ожиз хис қилишлари ва бунда ўзларини ўзгартира олмасликлари қўлидан кemasлиги сабаб бўлади ва энгиладилар. Бунинг учун нима қилиш керак лекин инсонлар эсларидан чиқарадиларки яна бир маротаба харакат қилиш керак, уриниб кўришга қўрқадилар. Ютуқга эришаолмасликни бошқарувчи омил бу қўрқувдир маслан: айтади (мени қўлимдан келмайди дейилади) ва энгилади ўзидаги қурқувга сабаб бўлаё тган омилга энгилади, ва харгал шундай қилишга одатланади хамда охир - оқибат бунга қўникади ва шу билан бирга буни одатга айлантиради.

Яна бир ютуқга эриша олмаслик омили бошқа инсонлар фикри бўйича рахбарга ё ки ўқитувчимизга ё қиш учун қилинадигон ишлар ва бу билан инсонлар агарда кимгадир ё қадигон иш қилмасам мен хафсиз бўла олмайман деган фикрда бўладилар шу билан инсонлар (самостоятельно) яъни эркин иш қилишга янгилакка интилишдан қўрқадилар. Қўрқувни энгиш, ютуқга эришишнинг энг осон ечими бу тартиб интизом хисобланади. Оддий инсонлар энгилроғини истайдилар ишининг ечимини энгил йўл билан хал қилишни хохлайдилар масалан бирон бир ишни қилишдан олдин ишни бажариш ўрнига оила даврасида ўтириб телевизор қўришни овқатланиб

кейин ё тиб ухлашни афзал топадилар, ва бу ишни харгал қилган сарингиз бу одатга айланади, хаё т шу тарзда давом этишига кўника бошлайсиз. Ютуғларга эришган инсонлар эса интизомга риоя қилган холда кунини ўткизади ва ўзларини ишига таълуқли ишлар билан шуғиллана бошлайди. Гё тэ Немец файласуфи шундай деган кейин осон бўлиши учун аввал қийин бўлади. Яхши одатларни ўзлаштириш қийин ва ўларни ўзида ушлаб яшаб кетиш осон эмас, ё мон одатлар эса жуда тез ўзлаштирилади ва яшаш осонроқ бўлади. Одатларни ўзгартириш учун инсонлар олдиларига мақсад кўйиши ва буни хар куни ўзи учун такроран такидлаб бориши ҳамда буни қайта –қайта ўқиб ё ки ё зиб ўзига сингдириб бориши лозим буни одатга айлантириши керак шунда онгимиз буни ўзига сингдириб боради ва шу мақсад тарзда ишлаё тганингизни ўзингиз ҳам сезмай қоласиз. Мақсадларингизни 1 йил 5 йил ё ки 10 йил олдинга режалаштириб ё зишингиз мумкин. Кундалик хаё тингизга айлантинг хар куни ўзингиз учун мақсад кўйинг. Мақсадга эришаё тган йўлингиз қийинга ўхшаб туюлсада мақсадингиздан кечманг, иш олдинга юрушмаябди деб хар кунги кўяё тган мақсадингизни унитиб кўйманг унга эришишни хохласангиз хар куни шу мақсадни олдингизга қайта –қайта кўяверинг ва албатта натижасини кўрасиз. Демак иш жараё нида, хаё т тарзида, бизнесда , ютуқларга эришиш учун (Зона камфорта) яъни хотиржамлик одатий иш тарзида ишлашдан бошқа поғонага кўтарилиш ва хамиша мақсад билан ишлашни бошлаш керак, ха бу аввалига осон бўлмайди лекин кейинчалик эса бу одатга айланади. Кунни аввал бажаришингиз керак бўлган мақсадларингизни ё зиш билан ва бугун қилмоқчи бўлган ишларингиз режаси билан бошланг шуни ўзингизга одат қилинг сўнг бу қоидаларга ва шу интизомга риоя этинг.

P.S. Шуни алохида айтиб ўтиш керакки олдингизга кўйган мақсадлирингиз амалга ошишига қатъий ишонч бўлсин ишонч бўлдими, бажармоқчи бўлган мақсадингиз амалаг ошади, асосийси ишончдир.

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MAHMUDXO'JA BEHBUDIYNING MILLAT G'AMIDA O'TKAZGAN IBRATLI UMRI

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Pedagogika fanlari bo__yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Mahmudxo__ja Behbudiyning ilmiy va ijodiy sohada olib borgan mashaqqatli izlanishlari, millatni uyg__otish sohasida olib borgan islohotlari haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Shuningdek, millatni ma'rifatli qilish uchun ilmiy maqolalar, avomning ilmdan uzoqlashib to__y-marakalarga berilganligi va avom dastidan chekkan uqubatlari yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *faoliyat, tarix, asr, hadis, umr, yaratish, ma'rifatpatvarlik, millatni uyg__otish, ilm-ma'rifatli qilish, yo__lga qo__yish, diniy, dunyoviy, azob, ilm, to__y va marakalar, isrof, yetim, taraqqiyot, qurbon.*

Hayot faoliyati davomida dunyoning ko__p davlatida bo__lib u yurtlardagi iqtisodiy va manaviy-ma'rifiy taraqqiyotni ko__rib, tarixda butun dunyoni titratib, butun dunyoga haligacha ustozlik qilayotgan buyuk Turkistonni ma'naviy va iqtisodiy qoloqlikdan qutqarishni hayotidagi eng oliy maqsadi deb bilgan, bu yo__lda qurbon bo__lishini bilaturib jiddu-jaht bilan hech bir to__siq va qiyinchiliklarga azob-uqubatlarga e'tibor bermay ilm-ma'rifat yo__lida qurbon bo__lgan Mahmudxo__ja Behbudiy juda oz atigi 45 yil umr ko__rdi. Bu oz umri davomida diniy va dunyoviy ilmlarni chuqur o__rganishga bel bog__ladi. Jahonda bo__layotgan voqea-hodisalar, jumladan, urushlar va ularning sababi, mohiyatini millat manfaati nuqtai nazaridan tafakkur chig__irig__idan o__tkazdi. Shu bilan birga tariximizning tanazzul bosqichlari, sabablarini taftish qildi.

Mahmudxo__ja Behbudiy ota-onasidan erta ajralib yetim holda ulg__aygan bo__lsada 25 yoshida Muftiylik maqomiga sazovor bo__ldi. Hayotinnig qolgan qismini, maraka-marosimlariga bor-budini sarflab boylari kerilib, faqirlari qarzga botib lekin farzandi ilm olishiga, sabot chiqarib ziyoli bo__lishiga sariq

chaqa sarflamagan avomning, taraqqiyotga tik boqmasdan tilidan bid'at, shirk, kufr sozlari tushmay muqaddas islomning asl mohiyatini tushunmay zamondan gofil qolgan dindorlarini yo lini to g irlashga sarfladi.

Ozi asos solgan —Oyna|| jurnalidagi maqolalarida, —Padarkush|| dramasida va ko plab asarlarida, ularni noto g ri yo lda ekanini amaliy va nazariy, diniy-dunyoviy ilmlar asosida isbotlab, ajoyib uslubda keng yoritib berdi. Ammo bunday sharafli xizmatlarni ilmsiz, johil avom qadriga yetmadi. Behbudiyga ayovsiz aziyat yetqazishdi.

Behbudiy ana shunday millat muammosini ta'kidlab bir maqolasida shunday yozadi; —Endi a'molimizg_a diqqat qilmoq kerak. Aksar xalqi- mizni a'moli shulki, ishlasa va foyda qilsa. Shoyadki, o g il va qizini to y qilsa va ham qanday! O z qatorindagi odamlarni qilgan to yidan ziyodaroq! Bechora kosibni a'moli to ydur. O zi rohat yuzi ko rmaydur. Kecha-kunduzni 18, balki 20 soatni mehnatg_a o tkaraturgon kosiblarimiz bordur. Haqqincha yemaydur, kiymaydur. O n va yigirma sanalar mehnat va mashaqqat etar va xudodan o g il tilar, to y qilmoq uchun. Ana, bechorani a'moli. Yigirma sanalik meqnati uch kun to yda tamom. Yana Ahmad porina qavli va xona girad. To y musrifi uchun qarz egalaridan qochadur. Katta to y qilib xotun olgon bir qism bechoralarni holig_a yig_lamoq kerak. Uch kunlik to yni azosi ba'zi oilalarda o n yil, hatto, bir umr surar, balki bevatan va xonavayronlikg_a sabab bo_lur. Bir kosibni akdu nikohig_a, to yu obro_sig_a ming so_m. Bir o rtahol uchun 2000 yo 3000 so_m. Nimboy uchun to rt-besh ming so_m kerak. Bu so mlarni yuzdan yetmish beshi yeyilib-ichilib... ketar. Bu so mlar aslinda kimniki edi? Bonka, firma, foydaxo_r- niki. Tabiiy, bularg_a pullarini bermoqlozim, na berilur? Bog_u xona va uyi ichindagi asbobni sotib bermoq kerak. Bechora kelin va kuyovni ko_rpa va libosig_acha sotilur, qarzxohg_a berilur||. Behbudiy XIX-asrning ikkinchi yarmida o_z maqolalarida muammo sifatida tahlil qilgan bu kabi odatlar bugungi kunimizning ham dolzarb masalalaridan biri bo_lib qolmoqda.

Behbudiy nazarida ma'rifat uchun birgina maktab kifoya qilmasdi. Zamon va dunyo voqealari bilan tanishib bormoq, millat va Vatanning kundalik hayotidan, ahvolidan, ogoh bo'lmoq kerak edi. Binobarin, millat uchun shunday oyna kerak ediki, unda u o'z qabohatini ham, malohatini ham ko'ra olsin. Mana shu ehtiyoj va zarurat Behbudiyini teatr va matbuot sari boshladi. —Padarkush|| shu tariqa maydonga keldi., 1911-yilda yozilgan

—Padarkush|| dramasi 1913-yildagina bosilib chiqadi. Kitob jildidagi «Borodino jangi va Rusiyaning fransuzlar bosqinidan xalos bo‘lishining yubiley sanasiga bag‘ishlanadi», degan yozuv va uning Tiflis senzurasining ruxsati bilan chop etilishi shuni ko‘rsatadiki, ish oson ko‘chmagan. Pyesa bosilib chiqqandan keyin ham uni sahnaga qo‘yish uchun yaqin bir yil vaqt ketdi. Muallif bu haqdagi xatlarga javoban kinoyaomuz: —Turkistonda bekor odam yo‘qki, xalq uchun ishlasa. Bekor kishi yo‘qki, teatru sahnasiga chiqib, —masxarabozlik|| qilsa|| , deb yozgan edi.

Behbudiy ana shunday keng fikr sohibi va zamonasida haqiqatni ochiq-oydin ayta oladigan o_z zamonasining ma‘rifatparvari edi. Bu zotning asriy orzu umidlari hozirda yangi O_zbekistonda amalga oshib bormoqda va allomaning buyuk xizmatlar qalbimizda mangu qolajak.

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FILM: ART OR INDUSTRY

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Annotation

This article provides a brief analysis of the modern film industry in Uzbekistan, highlighting the achievements and reforms that have been made. As a foreign experience, it is proposed to consider and compare the scientific works of Venice Film Festival director Luigi Chiarini, as the largest theorist of Italian cinema. The article describes the fundamental principles of his theory.

Key words: film theory, film industry, film art, presidential decree, reforms, achievements.

Introduction.

On April 7, 2021, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed the decision "On measures to raise the quality of Uzbekistan film industry to a new level and further improve the system of state support for filmmaking".[1] Many filmmakers who have served in our country say that this draft law is not only timely, but also as vital as air for our cinematography. The famous Uzbek director Ali Hamroyev said that our film industry was in a very difficult condition for many years before this measures were taken to improve whole filmmaking organisations from universities to ministry departments. Renovation and complete administrative reform were required. He says about this: "In the past 7 years, 4 film department directors have changed in the cinematography of Uzbekistan. New general director of the Agency, Firdavs Abdukholikov, has done a great job with a small team of like-minded people for the short time. So on the president's table, appeared a detailed and enthusiastic law project for a truly revolutionary development of our long-suffering film industry. Now it is a responsible and not easy task - to justify the trust of movie fans and the head of state." [2]

Discussion.

During the Soviet period, Uzbekistan's film industry always held a leading position in terms of the volume and quality of films produced per year. So, looking back, we would witness a rich film heritage, unfortunately, the quality level of film production changed during the years of Independence. Many film experts and members of international organizations such as FIPRESCI have repeatedly pointed out that Uzbek film industry has an aesthetic movement towards Bollywood, mass production without losing its local originality. Of course, if there is a demand from the audience, whether it is a series or a comedy, any creative product has the right to live. But if we compare all this with the masterpieces of the past Soviet years, we understand that we need to look for other noteworthy landmarks. Fortunately, after a long period of stagnation, our country has realized the need to focus on this area, as evidenced by the Presidential Decree, so we can see the results. The buildings were renovated, the newest equipment and tools were purchased, and a new international festival was organized.

It seems that all conditions have been created for quality production. But sometimes, even under ideal conditions, the problem of quality is not the conditions and the equipment, but the lack of education. In order to understand ourselves, our interests and where we are moving, we need to study the experience and history of other countries to look at ourselves from the outside.

Proposal.

How has the foreign film industry developed in difficult times? The famous Italian cinematographer Luigi Chiarini in his scientific theoretical work "Cinema: Industry or Art" provides a research solution to these problems. His theory gives us a vivid picture of the specific historical conditions, which is a reflection of the conditions of the foreign film industry.

Luigi Chiarini (1900-1975) is an Italian film theorist, film director, director of the Venice Festival (1963-1968). He created several scientific works on the theory of cinema, besides, he was the founder and editor of the magazines Bianco nero (1937), Rivista del cinema italiano (1952). [3]

Chiarini was one of the ideologists and creators of Italian neorealism. [4]

He was one of the fighters for the creative independence of Italian film industry workers. He came to cinema during the years of fascist reaction, when any form of progressive creative thought was persecuted, and Italian screens were dominated by films glorifying fascist expansion and colonial plunder. Honest Italian film critics, directors and screenwriters were deprived of the opportunity to create true cinema that truly reflect the life of the Italian people under fascist Italy. Refusing to cooperate with fascist propagandists, they limited themselves to creative and theoretical experiments in the spirit of bourgeois innovation.

Only after the Second World War, when the political situation in Italy changed, a group of progressive creators, including Chiarini, finally had the opportunity to create truly artistic, realistic cinematography.

The best of them abandoned their prejudices and delusions and took a position of realism.

After the WW2, Chiarini managed the progressive film magazines "Bianco e Nero" and "Rivista del Film Italiano" for several years, and took an active part in the work of the Film Club of Rome, which united the leading Italian filmmakers. Chiarini's book is a perfectly evident of the reactionary bureaucratic censorship system that restricts the creative freedom of Italian artists, the dictatorship of Catholic reaction that tries to enslave Italian cinema to the interests of the Vatican. Analyzing organizational structure of the Italian film industry, Chiarini comprehensively reveals the direct connection of the leaders of the Italian cinematography with the government and the Vatican, and the wholesale speculators who opened a wide path to Italian

screens for imported dirty films. The protectionist system of state subsidies and bonuses leads to the loss of large sums of money, most of which always end up in the pockets of Westerners and speculators. Built on the principle of mismanagement: producers tried to overpay competing "movie stars" while underpaying props or day laborers.

In Italy, the strong campaign between Catholic reactionary forces and pro-democracy forces also affected the film industry. In his book, Chiarini describes in detail the ideological period when were created favorable conditions for reactionary and religious films.

Considering that filmmaking requires extensive technical equipment and huge investments, the art of cinema is also born of free and voluntary action, so it is fatally caught between the rock and the anvil of political and economic life.

Results.

There are some items for developing cinema industry on flourishing fulfilling level. One of them ideological freedom. To clarify his point, Chiarini analyses film industry in three main aspects.

The first aspect claims high quality technical equipment of film studios, workers and specialists, just as an artist needs to create his work. "film studios should be a suitable tool for creating quality creative work."

The second aspect film scripts should be prepared as piece of qualified literature novel. At this stage, ignorance and bad script leads to a decrease the artistic level, which is reflected on production.

The third aspect is industry and commerce; So, in two limitations we find film studios and cinema theatres as printing houses and bookstores: "in cinema there are artists and distributors, in the book business there are writers and booksellers". This third aspect, should not be confused with creativity.

Each aspect has its own governing laws. Film Art is individuality, personality,

differentiation, Film Industry is uniformity, standardization, typification.

Conclusion.

The problem of cinema is that the confusion of the three aspects leads to the fusion of the considerations of the industrial order with the artistic. Chiarini clarifies the functions of the producer: the producer should not be considered as a capitalist, but as "the person who unites production". How much capital do you need to make a film to make your work? In a word, a real producer is a person who provides material support to the creator . A film producer can also be considered an artist because he contributes to the creation of a work of art through his financial techniques, but he must be able to understand the spirit and meaning of the his own filmmaking process. The idea of a film is a moral; therefore, "according to the idea of the film, the director should give a certain meaning to the audiovisual product and show its own experience and superficial things to dramatize the power of the idea.

Chiarini defines: "In order to take its proper place in the field of cinematography, it is necessary to show moral and political ideas and feelings." Cinema is the result of collaboration, the idea of the film industry is to bring together different partners to achieve a unity of inspiration and create high qualified movies."

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